

Masterthesis

Deep Learning Image segmentation for *Pseudomonas fluorescens SBW25*

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Abstract

Pseudomonas fluorescens strain SBW25 is a model organism for microbial population biology, ecology, and evolution. Fluorescence microscopy and phase contrast microscopy are employed to characterize phenotypical and morphological traits in response to genetic modifications, externally induced selection pressure, varying physical or chemical environmental conditions and competition. Due to the vast amount of image data, automated analysis methods need to be implemented to measure cell numbers, shape, and size and to track these observables over time. The present master thesis project aims at implementing an image segmentation workflow based on deep artificial neural networks suitable for microscopy images taken of individual cells and cell cultures of *Pseudomonas fluorescens* SBW25. Starting from the deep learning code DeLTA 2.0, we retrain a deep neural network using a curated training and test dataset of our model organism. We evaluate our model using various figures of merit and compare to results obtained with the original DeLTA 2.0 model which was trained on image data from *Escherichia coli* strains. Our retrained model yields a significant improvement in the intercept-over-union figure of merit which characterizes the predictive power of the model.

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1 Motivation

The amount of data gathered in various fields, non-scientific and scientific has grown enormously over the last 20 years, creating opportunities for new insights by mining this data as well as challenges of Big Data. The capacities to gather data are expected to continue growing rapidly [1]. Biology is one of the most prolific data producers among sciences [2].

The increasing efficiency in creating more data in shorter amounts of time, creates various challenges, which require methods of information technology to be applied. These challenges concern the complete 'life cycle' of data, acquisition, storage, distribution and analysis [1] and are not limited to a specific data type.

One of the earliest fields to recognize the potential of neural networks in biology was protein structure prediction, applying them since the 1980s [3] leading to the development of AlphaFold, a DL approach for protein prediction which is considered a breakthrough [4]. In 2012 a deep learning model won the MERCK Molecular Activity Challenge, generating increased interest in the potential applications of deep learning in the life sciences [5].

The interdisciplinary work of biology and information technology has created the scientific field of bioinformatics. Bioinformatics is mostly associated with protein structure prediction and DNA sequencing and prediction. The techniques used in bioinformatics can for example be used in genomics, a research field aiming to understand the genomes of different species [6].

“The intersection of Deep Learning and genomic research may lead to a profound understanding of genomics that will benefit multiple fields including medicine, pharmacy and even agriculture.” [6, S.2]

Besides genomic and proteomic sequence data, image data is a key data source, in particular microscopy images are used for biological research purposes. The number of biological images acquired in digital form is growing as rapidly as other forms of data [7].

Considering the value that the analysis of image data provides to find answers to biological problems, bioimage informatics can be considered a new area of bioinformatics [7].

Biological image data is analysed for various purposes, e.g. analysis of cellular phenotypes to determine gene function, understanding the dynamic processes in cells and living organisms or reconstructing the 3D neural structures and wiring diagram of a brain [7].

At the Department for Microbial Population Biology (MPB) at the Max-Planck-Institute for Evolutionary Biology the focus of most research is the model organism *Pseudomonas fluorescens* strain SBW25 [8,9]. *Pseudomonas fluorescens* is a common bacterial inhabitant of soil and water. Interest in this particular organism stems from potential benefits for host plants, e.g. in an agricultural context. One branch of research aims at characterizing genetically modified derivatives in terms of cell size and shape, metabolism, growth dynamics, evolutionary fitness, and ecology. Microscopy images are segmented to identify individual cells followed by cell counting, size and shape analysis, classification and tracking in the case of time resolved data. Measurements of timelapse-microscopy images leads to valuable understanding of gene expressions and environmental influences [10].

Timelapse-microscopy of bacteria produces large amounts of data. Manual image data analysis would be too time consuming to cope with the data, therefore automated analysis methods are needed. Artificial Intelligence (AI), specifically Deep Learning (DL) have shown promis-

ing results in performing segmentation, classification, and tracking [11] more efficiently and with lower error rates than manual workflows [12].

Several research groups have developed tools for their projects to complete DL tasks for their specific problem and even though these tools exist and are available, groups continue to develop their own solutions, because the existing ones doesn't match the specific problem they are facing [13] and accuracy is a major concern handling research data, which to achieve, needs a model fitting the problem.

Often a research group doesn't have the resources to develop a solution from scratch. The goal of this study is to provide a way to adapt an existing tool, developed for a similar task on a different model organism, to perform the given task on the model organism *Pseudomonas fluorescens* used at the MPB.

For this the tool DeLTA 2.0 will be used [10,14]. Beforehand tools for image segmentation have been researched and several tools have been considered and evaluated. The choice to use DeLTA 2.0 is based on the fact that DeLTA is developed especially for the analysis of timelapse microscopy and does already offers analysis mechanisms following segmentation, hence the tool could be used for further analysis. Furthermore DeLTA 2.0 is still under active development and provides an active support and help on their gitlab repository. DeLTA 2.0 being python based is also platform independent and a change in the system architecture will not result in a need to move to another tool.

This thesis is structured as follows: The theoretical basics of DL in general, image segmentation, and DeLTA 2.0 are going to be explained in the first chapters to establish a deeper understanding of DL and the given model which is necessary to understand the DL process and be able to adjust parameters if necessary. Following this the practical part of this study can be split into 4 different phases.

Phase 1 will be the installation of DeLTA 2.0 and providing a stable runtime environment. This is going to be evaluated by running provided scripts and test data of the originally used model organism, that is provided by the developers of DeLTA 2.0.

Phase 2 will be data preparation. For this a workflow has to be established to build a annotated dataset, including an analysis of the file formats used, image sizes and if needed pre-processing and file conversion. The images have to be annotated for training purposes. The annotated data is going to be split into a training and a test dataset.

Phase 3 will be the retraining of the model. This requires multiple steps. The initial examination of the model will now be useful to understand the parts of the pipeline and generate scripts.

Phase 4 will be the evaluation of predicted segmentation maps by the model. The goal being to reach the same or even better performance on the new model organism.

2 Image Segmentation

Image segmentation is the process of dividing an image into homogeneous segments. This process creates a representation of the image that allows for the analysis of the objects of interest. The process of image segmentation can be considered the most important and crucial part of image analysis, since its results are used in the next steps of the analysis. Hence a wrong segmentation will affect the subsequent steps, e.g. classification or object measurements [15]. There are various fields of application in which image segmentation is relevant, scene understanding, medical image analysis, robotic perception, video surveillance, augmented reality and image compression to name just a few [16].

2.1 Semantic segmentation and instance segmentation

Semantic image segmentation is the process in which each pixel of an image gets assigned a class [17, 18]. In case of this project that means a binary classification of each pixel, labeling the pixel as *belonging to a bacterial cell* or *not belonging to a bacterial cell*. This is called semantic segmentation, resulting in a mask for the associated image.

(a) Image from time-lapse microscopy *Pseudomonas Fluorescence* SBW25.

(b) Image segmentation mask, semantic segmentation.

Figure 1: Visualization of semantic segmentation.

Figure 1 visualizes semantic segmentation. The image is a timepoint extracted from a timelapse microscopy on *Pseudomonas fluorescens* SBW25 done by the MPI team.

The semantics are dependent on the data and the problem that is supposed to be solved, i.e. there is a difference in a detection of human, where the whole body is the object to be segmented, and a motion detection, where it is essential, that different body parts are segmented as different objects [19].

The term instance segmentation is often used in recent literature, describing a joint task of segmentation and detection. Even though the combined task can be performed by current neural network architectures with a single network like the Recurrent Neural Network

proposed in *Recurrent Neural Networks for Semantic Instance Segmentation* [20], instance segmentation is a combination of tasks. The result of instance segmentation is not only a mask of the image in which each pixel is labeled with an object class it belongs to, but each object of a class is identified as an instance, i.e. multiple object of the same class are differentiated [21].

(a) Image from time-lapse microscopy *Pseudomonas Fluorescens* SBW25.

(b) Image segmentation mask, semantic segmentation.

Figure 2: Visualization of instance segmentation.

Figure 2 visualizes instance segmentation on the same image as seen in figure 1.

2.2 Traditional segmentation techniques

Knowledge about how an image is segmented and which techniques are applied helps to understand the learning process of a Neural Network (Machine Learning (NN)), evaluate the capabilities and limitations of DL and helps data preparation. Furthermore for training a dataset needs to be segmented. To limit the amount of manual labour necessary, these techniques might be helpful. For these reasons we are briefly introducing some traditional segmentation techniques. There are various other segmentation techniques used and more detailed explanations, for the purpose of this work, we just introduce the key concepts of the traditional techniques. For further reading [22] and [15] are good starting points.

Algorithms for image segmentation use characteristics, that are similar to the process of sight and recognition. Characteristics that determine the recognition of an object can be color, form, texture or intensity [22]. Segmentation Algorithms can be classified as threshold-based, boundary-based and region-based segmentation [15].

2.2.1 Threshold-based segmentation

Threshold-based segmentation, also called pixel-based segmentation, decides for each pixel if it belongs to an object or not. Thresholds can be used globally or locally, which allows multiple thresholds for the same image [22]. The setting of the threshold can be done

manually or calculated, usually the histogram, i.e. statistical distribution of tone values [23] is used to find the threshold. Threshold-based algorithms are sensitive to noise and the determination of the right threshold can be difficult [15].

2.2.2 Edge-based segmentation

Edge-based segmentation algorithms identify edges in the image to get the boundaries of objects, using the images gradient. The main approach is the assumption of a change in the characteristics of pixels at the edge of an an object [22]. Edge-based segmentation is sensitive to noise and fails to detect hardly recognizable edges due to the low change in characteristics [15].

2.2.3 Region-based segmentation

Region-based segmentation detect objects by similarity and connectivity of pixels, using calculations of the average from a region as comparison [22]. This can be done by region growing, region splitting or clustering [15].

2.3 Segmentation in CNNs

Convolutional neural networks (CNNs) are a NN architecture commonly used for image processing [11]. Chapter 3 will describe the basics of DL and network architectures. While traditional segmentation techniques are getting good results in some cases and are valuable for helping preparing training data, they have downsides. For one they are heavily dependant on the quality of the images and on the consistency of features like brightness and contrast of the pictures being consistent, if the settings are not to be set anew for each image. Another drawback is, that these feature-based approaches rely on the quality of the features, extracted by the expert. Humans tend to miss latent or abstract features. DL solves this problem, since the network learns features itself [19].

Even though the network learns features on its own and is better in recognizing latent and abstract features and, if trained for that to cope with differentiation in lighting and noise, it is using the same characteristics the traditional segmentation techniques are relying on. Hence the knowledge of these techniques and the characteristics is essential when setting up experiments.

Figure 3: Example of an image and what the first 32 filters in the first convolution layer of a DL network are generating as output [11].

As figure 3 shows, the CNN is using image manipulation to find characteristics. If we consider an edge for example, this is still determined by the characteristics of pixels that a traditional edge-based segmentation approach would consider like having an abrupt change of brightness or saturation between pixels. This illustrates, that DL segmentation is not magic in a black box that can work miracles and characteristics have to be considered when taking images.

2.4 Image segmentation metrics

To objectively determine how well a segmentation task was performed it has to be measurable; for this purpose metrics are used. Following some metrics commonly used for image segmentation are introduced. For calculating these metrics there has to be a ground truth, which means, for the predicted segmentation mask there has to be a segmentation mask, that is seen as true. More details about test datasets and ground truth can be found in chapter 3.4 and chapter 6.

For class wise calculations which resemble a binary classification, important terms for comparison of ground truth and prediction are [11]:

- TP: True Positive, the pixels were correctly predicted belonging to the class.
- TN: True negative, the pixels were correctly classified as not belonging to the class.
- FP: False positive, the pixels were falsely predicted as belonging to the class.
- FN: False Negative: The pixels were falsely predicted as not belonging to the class.

2.4.1 Accuracy

Pixel accuracy describes the ratio of pixels which are classified correctly, divided by the number of all pixels in the image.

The PA can be calculated for each class separately using.

$$PA = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^K p_{ii}}{\sum_{i=1}^K \sum_{j=1}^K p_{ij}} \quad (1)$$

$$PA = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^K p_{ii}}{\sum_{i=1}^K \sum_{j=1}^K p_{ij}}$$

Where K is the number of classes, i.e. in our binary pixel classification, where the pixel either is belonging to a cell or it is not belonging to the cell are 2 classes. p_{ii} is the number of correctly classified pixels, i.e. belonging to class i and predicted to belong to class i , in our binary classification this equals $TP + TN$. p_{ij} is the number of pixel belonging to class i , but being predicted as belonging to class j , in our binary classification this equals $FP + FN$ [16, 24, 25].

Mean Pixel Accuracy extends the pixel accuracy, the pixel accuracy is calculated per class and then averaged over the number of classes.

$$MPA = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{i=1}^K \frac{p_{ii}}{\sum_{j=1}^K p_{ij}} \quad (2)$$

The results of pixel accuracy can be misleading if the class representation is small, in which case pixel accuracy mainly provides results on the identification of the class not being present, i.e. the pixel accuracy score is giving good results without actually giving insight if the class is predicted correctly [18, 25].

Accuracy can also be measured distance-based, where the distance between the boundary in the prediction and the ground truth is used. Different approaches of calculations like mean squared distance and mean absolute distance, root mean squared distance and maximum distance exist [26, 27].

2.4.2 Intersection over Union

Intersection over Union (IoU), also called the **Jaccard Index** is a metric which is commonly used [16] and implemented in Python libraries like scikit-learn [28]. IoU measures the intersection of the predicted segmentation map and the segmentation map of the ground truth divided by the union between the predicted segmentation map and the ground truth segmentation map.

$$IoU = J(A, B) = \frac{|A \cap B|}{|A \cup B|} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN + FP} \quad (3)$$

Where A is the ground truth segmentation map and B is the predicted segmentation map.

The IoU is calculated class wise, for the **Mean IoU** the IoU for each class is calculated and then the average of the results is calculated [16, 25].

2.4.3 Precision/Recall/F1 score

Precision, also called **Positive Predictive Value (PPV)**, is the probability that when the prediction is that a pixel belongs to the class, the pixel does belong to the class [29].

$$PPV = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (4)$$

The **Negative Predictive Value (NPV)**, can also be calculated class wise and is the probability that the prediction of a pixel not belonging to the class is correct $NPV = \frac{TN}{TN+FN}$ [29].

Recall, also called **True Positive Rate (TPR)** or **sensitivity**, is the probability that a pixel belonging to the class in the ground truth will be predicted as belonging to the class [29].

$$TPR = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (5)$$

The **True Negative Rate (TNR)**, or **specificity**, can be calculated likewise $TNR = \frac{TN}{TN+FP}$ [29].

Furthermore the **False Positive Rate (FPR)** $FPR = \frac{FP}{FP+TN}$ and the **False Negative Rate (FNR)** $FNR = \frac{FN}{FN+TP}$ can be determined [29].

Precision, Recall and F1 score are metrics which are calculated class wise and are connected.

Which metric should be calculated and used for evaluation is dependent on the problem to be solved and which errors need to be identified. In cases of binary classification, where false positives and false negatives can't be eliminated by better settings or training, there is a trade-off for precision and recall, i.e. by reducing the number of false positives, precision increases, the number of false negatives increases, recall drops [11].

The **F1 Score**, or **harmonic mean**, is a metric combining precision and recall. The f1 score is going to be low when precision and recall are low and will be high when precision and recall are high, i.e. the f1 score will approach 1 as errors decline [11].

$$F1Score = \frac{2 * Precision * Recall}{Precision + Recall} \quad (6)$$

There are more, at this point less common metrics like **Informedness** and **Markedness** that can be consulted for evaluating how well the prediction is doing and to evaluate which errors are made [29].

2.4.4 Dice Coefficient

The **Dice Coefficient (DC)** is a metric often used in medical image analysis and is positively correlated with the IoU. The IoU score measures closer to the worst case performance, while the DC measures closer to average performance [16, 25].

$$DC = \frac{2 | A \cap B |}{| A | + | B |} \quad (7)$$

Where A is the ground truth segmentation map and B is the predicted segmentation map. For binary classification the DC is identical to the F1 score as defined in equation 6 [16].

$$DC = \frac{2 * TP}{2 * TP + FP + FN} = \frac{2 * Precision * Recall}{Precision + Recall} = F1Score \quad (8)$$

2.4.5 Performance metrics

When using DL approaches, evaluation can be made not only for the result, but also other performance measures can be evaluated. Examples that are important to determine are used resources like runtime and memory used. Furthermore, metrics like needed lines of code for running a task could be determined. Since these measurements are highly dependant on the hardware, data and model used and are offering real value for comparison with other setups, most of the research work so far focuses on the metrics specific to the result specific metrics [16].

3 Deep Learning

DL is a specialisation of Machine Learning (Machine Learning (ML)), hence a part of Artificial Intelligence (AI). NNs are not a recent development, research going back as early as the 1950s, though the lack of efficient ways to train big networks prevented advances in the field until the 1980s. Since the 1990s NNs gained wide popularity and have achieved remarkable results in solving problems whose solutions seem natural and intuitive to humans. Some examples are image classification, speech transcription, handwriting transcription, ability to answer natural language questions [30].

The models in DL are called neural networks and even though these artificial neural networks are not models of the human brain some concepts were inspired by our understanding of the brain [30].

In biology the term neuron is applied to a variety of complex cells, figure 4 shows the inspiration for artificial neural networks.

Figure 4: Biological neuron compared to an artificial neuron [31].

We are simplifying neurons as information processing units. A neuron receives information in form of electrical signals. Signals received in a short interval are added, compared to a threshold and if the sum exceeds the threshold the neuron sends a new signal, which is received by another neuron, building a neural network. Figure 5 shows the connection of neurons which very abstracted can be compared to the communication between biological neurons.

Figure 5: Biological synapse compared to artificial neural network synapses [31].

An artificial neural network is built from artificial neurons, called perceptrons. A perceptron receives inputs and each input x_i is multiplied with the weight w_j of the connection over which it was received and a bias, which is a number belonging to the specific neuron, is added. The weights are defining how steep the curve to visualize the function is drawn, while the bias allows to shift the curve to the left or the right, to better fit the data [32]. All weighted inputs are summed

$$\sum_{i=1}^n x_i w_i + b_i \quad (9)$$

Equation 9 being the output of the perceptron that is passed to an activation function, which determines the further passing on of the signal, more on activation is described in chapter 3.1.2. The weights and the bias are the only changeable part of the network and are adjusted during training to get the desired output [11, 33]. Figure 6 shows the functionality of an artificial perceptron. Each input x is multiplied with a weight w , all weighted inputs are summed and the sum is handed over to an activation function y_i .

Figure 6: Perceptron with inputs, weights, bias and activation function [34].

The term deep in Deep Learning refers to the use of successive layers of computation, the number of layers being the depth of a model. While in previous ML techniques feature engineering was a manual task, DL automates it. The essential characteristics of DL are the incremental, layer-by-layer way in which increasingly complex representation are developed, and that the intermediate representations are learned jointly, each layer being updated considering the needs of the layer above and below [30].

Multiple factors have contributed to the recent interest and application of DL. One factor being the advances in Hardware making DL more accessible, especially Graphics processing unit (GPU) support, i.e. allowing calculation on the GPU [23], making a huge difference in computation time. Another factor is data available, data being gathered faster and more often shared. Various DL datasets of high quality are freely available to use. Also worth mentioning are better algorithms to train DL networks [30].

There are various architectures for DL, one especially suited and widely used and adapted for image processing is the CNN architecture [35]. There are various other architectures that are build for image analysis and image segmentation, e.g. recurrent networks or visual attention models. The model used in this work is based on a convolution network and an encoder-decoder architecture [16]. Hence we are going to investigate these architectures.

3.1 Convolutional Neural Networks

CNNs are one of the most successful architectures in DL and widely used, especially in image processing tasks [16].

David H. Hubel and Thorsten Wiesel discovered certain properties of the neurons in the visual cortex.

- Many neurons react on a small section of the visual field and have a local field of perception.
- The fields of perception of neurons can overlap.
- There are neurons having the same field of perception that react different, i.e. one neuron may react to horizontal lines, while another neuron may react to point-like stimuli.
- There are neurons with a larger field of perception that react to more complex stimuli.

To transfer these properties to a NN architecture, the network does not need to be fully connected, but has to be layered, where each layer reacts to the output of the previous one. These findings led to the development of *Neocognitron* in 1980 and with advances in technology in 1998 the development of CNN [33].

Figure 7 shows the typical architecture of a CNN.

Figure 7: CNN architecture [33]

Considering this work is concerned with image segmentation we're focusing on the feature learning part of the architecture.

The feature learning part typically consists of a sequence, that can be repeated and is made from

1. Convolutional layer
2. Activation layer
3. Pooling layer [33].

3.1.1 Convolutional layer

The convolutional layer applies a filter to extract features like lines, points, edges etc. from an image [33]. The term feature is also used for a piece of information about the content of an image, i.e. a pixel in an image. In literature with regard to CNNs the term feature is established for a particular structure in an input that a filter tries to detect, a characteristic, hence the term feature has always to be put in context.

Convolution is the process in which a filter, which is the operation of a neuron to detect a characteristic is swept over the input. This combined task can be referred to as convolution filter. To speed up the process multiple neurons can be assigned to perform the same operation simultaneously, sharing their weights [11]. Since it is often useful to consider the pixels next to a pixel, a square of weights, e.g. 3x3, serves as the filter kernel. The filter kernel is applied, where the square is centered over each pixel in turn. The size of the filter kernel is called the footprint. If the center of the kernel is placed on a pixel at the edge of an image, there are no input elements for all kernel elements. The solutions are to allow the kernel only be placed where it is within the image, which shrinks the image with each convolutional layer, or to add a padding to the image [11]. In figure 8 the principle of convolution is visualized.

Figure 8: Principle of a 3x3 convolution [36]

The filters used in the convolution simulate the neurons in the visual cortex as described in chapter 3.1. Like these biological neurons the filters detect specific patterns and pass on their output, called a feature map, to later filters [11].

A convolution layer is the assembly of different filters which are applied independently to the input tensor and their outputs are combined to create a new output tensor. A tensor is an array with any number of dimensions, i.e. a 3 dimensional tensor can be thought of as a cuboid. Each filter creates an image with one channel, creating an output with as many channels as filters were applied. This can not only increase the number of channels, but it can also be used to reduce the numbers of channels. Filters are hierarchical; in each new layer the output of the previous layer is taken as input. The detected characteristics are taken to detect further characteristics. The values of the filter kernels are improved in the training process [11].

Unlike a fully-connected network, CNNs only connect layers locally, creating small neighborhoods called receptive fields. This stacks layers in pyramids in which the receptive field increasingly widens [16]. Hence, where dense connected layers learn global patterns, convolution layers learn local patterns. This creates two properties:

- Learned patterns are translation-invariant, i.e. a learned pattern is recognized at

another location in the image, without relearning the pattern, like a dense connected layer would have to.

- Ability to learn spatial hierarchies of patterns, i.e. an early convolution layer learns small local patterns, the next layer will learn larger patterns made of the features of the previous layer [30].

This means that in a CNN the earlier layers capture local features like a contour producing sharper activations and the later layers capture more global features like a human, the activation being less sharp in comparison to the earlier layers [19]. Figure 9 shows an image after processed by activation maps from different layers.

Figure 9: Input image and activation maps. The top row shows activation maps from earlier layers, the bottom row shows activations from later layers [19]

3.1.2 Activation layer

The activation layer applies an activation function on the feature maps [16]. An activation takes a floating-point number as input and returns a new floating-point number [11] and influences the learning of the network [33]. Activation functions are non-linear to enable the network to learn complex functions. Non-linear functions are functions where the output is not directly proportional to the input, so every function not creating a linear graph is a non-linear function [29]. In theory another activation function could be applied to every neuron, but usually in practice the same activation function is applied for all neurons [11].

For CNNs and therefore in image processing the most commonly used activation function is the rectified linear unit (Rectified linear unit (ReLU))

$$f_{act}(c) = f_{ReLU}(c) = \max(0, c) \quad (10)$$

with c being the sum of the weighted inputs which is calculated by equation 9. This is setting a threshold, where the signal is only passed on, if the input value c is greater than 0 [33]. Figure 10 visualizes ReLU.

Figure 10: ReLU, it outputs 0 for all negative inputs, otherwise it outputs the input [33].

The ReLU activation function is a fast and simple function to include nonlinearity. The fact that for every negative input an output of 0 is generated can generate the problem that changes in the input don't lead to changes in the output, hence the network stops learning. To solve this, there are variations of ReLU, like leaky ReLU, parametric ReLU, shifted ReLU or exponential ReLU [11]. There are various other activation functions used in DL, some other popular activation functions are sigmoid and tanh. At this stage there is no firm theory, which activation function produces the best results in specific layer of a specific network in a given scenario. Best practice is to start with an activation functions, that has produced good results in similar set ups and try alternatives to observe the changes in performance [11].

3.1.3 Pooling layer

The process of pooling, or downsampling, changes the height and width of the input images. One advantage is that this makes the data flow faster, reducing computing time, needed resources and energy. Another advantage is that it can make some operations, e.g. classification, more accurate. The increase in accuracy results from pooling having the effect of blurring an image, which allows each filter element to see more of the input [11]. The inspiration for pooling lies in the concept of lateral inhibition from neurobiology, where an active neuron inhibits the activity of a neighboring neuron [33].

Pooling methods used are max pooling and average pooling, max pooling being the more commonly used one due to the fact that experience has shown that networks using max pooling learn quicker than networks using average pooling [11, 36]. Figure 11 illustrates the functionality of max pooling. A 2x2 filter selects the maximum value to keep and deletes the others.

Figure 11: Max Pooling principle [36].

Instead of having dedicated pooling layers the pooling step can be integrated into the convolution process. This is called striding, where the filter is not applied to each pixel but moves, or strides, more than one pixel, skipping the pixels in between, resulting in a smaller output image. This combined process usually runs faster. Even though mostly the output of striding and using dedicated layers are roughly the same, this is not always the case, and in some given datasets and architectures, the use of dedicated convolutional layers and pooling layers works better. The architecture cannot just be changed from one approach to another because the filters produced from striding are usually different from the ones produced from convolution followed by pooling. For changing the architecture, the network would have to be retrained [11].

3.2 Evolution of CNNs

Since the introduction of CNNs they have been greatly improved with different techniques. Some examples are layer-wise training, rectified linear activations and skip-connections. Several network architectures for different purposes were developed, using convolutions. Some of these architectures were designed especially for image segmentation. Knowing which models are available helps to determine which is appropriate for the problem at hand and applying them. Furthermore understanding the underlying techniques and knowing why the models were designed the way they are helps not only using a network but might enable the user to adjust the model for better performance for the given task [19].

The model used in this project is based on U-Net, which I will introduce in chapter 4.1, a widely known and used encoder-decoder model for biological image segmentation [10, 16].

3.3 Convolutional encoder-decoder

Convolutional encoder-decoder architectures are using up-convolutions to map each pixel of the input to a pixel of the output. For this, the generated output is up-sampled to the size of the input image. The encoding part of the architecture is a CNN architecture, the decoder part uses upsampling, or unpooling, and up-convolution, to increase the resolution of the output for mapping the pixels [36].

3.3.1 Upsampling

Upsampling is also called unpooling, since it is the counterpart for pooling. For this there exists a upsampling layer corresponding to a pooling layer, which decompresses a pixel to a neighborhood of pixels, corresponding to the compression made by the pooling layer, i.e. if a 2×2 pooling layer was used, compressing 2×2 pixels to one, the 2×2 upsampling layer decompresses 1 pixel back to 2×2 pixels [19].

Figure 12: Upsampling with max unpooling technique [37].

There are different techniques for upsampling. Nearest neighbor, bi-linear interpolation, bed of nails and max unpooling. The process of max pooling and max unpooling is shown in figure 12. Max unpooling saves the index of the maximum value in the downsampling process, this is done for every max pooling layer in the encoding path. In the decoding path the index is used to map the value in the corresponding max unpooling layer, filling the other spaces with zeros. Other techniques can lead to inconsistencies in the classification, especially in the boundary region. Hence for segmentation tasks, especially segmentation with sensitive borders like cluster of bacteria, max unpooling gives better results [19].

3.3.2 Up-convolution

Up-convolution is a convolution, where the number of channels is reduced. As described in chapter 3.1.1 a regular convolution cannot only increase the number of channels, but reduce them too. As in the encoder path, the tasks of the decoding path can be combined. The combination of upsampling and convolution is called transposed convolution or fractional striding [11]. The term deconvolution can be found, but is misleading, since deconvolution is not correct in a mathematical definition [36] and the term deconvolution also refers to a different idea [38].

3.4 Training and Evaluation

DL learns features by itself, i.e. it discovers rules to make decisions on its own and the features don't have to be selected by humans. The algorithm learns these features by extracting patterns from input data on which it evaluates new given data [11]. The way a network learns is by adjusting the weights of the connections and the bias of the perceptrons that were described in chapter 3. There are 3 ways how DL algorithms can learn [33].

3.4.1 Supervised Learning

The method of learning used in this work and also the most commonly used method in DL at this point is **supervised learning**. In supervised learning a training dataset is prepared where for the input data a label is provided. For the learning of image segmentation tasks a training dataset consists of a set of images in which for each image a prepared segmentation

mask is provided. In the training process the network adjust its weights based on this training data. Based on these learned weights new data is labeled [11].

3.4.2 Unsupervised Learning

In **unsupervised learning** the algorithms learn about relationships between data instead of a relationship between data and a label. This is used for clustering or grouping data that is related. Hence this method is also referred to as clustering. This can also be used for improving the quality of data like removing noise from images or compress data [11].

3.4.3 Reinforcement Learning

Reinforcement Learning uses a trial and error approach. The system tries an approach and the result is given a score. The system is basically rewarded for good actions and punished for actions with bad results like often used in computer games. After getting lots of scores the approach leading to the best results can be selected. When patterns change over time, new approaches can be tested and the one with the best score is kept [11].

3.4.4 Training process

The model used in this work is based on supervised learning, hence we are going to describe the learning process for this process.

To learn the network is presented with a set of training data. For each example the network makes a prediction which is compared to the ground truth. The ground truth is a label prepared by manual labour which is seen as the truth. In our case this is a segmentation mask belonging to the image. Based on the difference Δ the weights are adjusted [33].

The training consists of 6 steps in two main phases:

1. Choosing start values, often randomly, for the weights and biases.
2. Letting the network make predictions on a set of training data.
3. Determining the difference with the ground truth by calculating the loss.
4. Propagating the loss backwards through the network.
5. Updating the weights and biases based on the information obtained through backpropagation to reduce the loss.
6. Iterating steps 2 to 5 until the model is considered 'good'.

The first phase is called **forwardpropagation**, when the network makes a prediction for a training sample. The training sample is passed through the network, each neuron in each layer applies their transformation until the final layer produces an output, i.e. labeled data, in case of image segmentation a segmentation mask, hence a label for each pixel. The prediction is compared to the ground truth given. To calculate the difference a **loss function** is used [34]. The loss function used depends on the problem and a lot of research is done developing new loss functions. Despite that ongoing research there are some standard loss functions that have proven to do well in most cases like **absolute loss**, **mean squared error** and **cross-entropy** [29]. The loss function used in the model used in this thesis is going to be described in section 4.1 and section 4.3. The result Δ of the loss function should be close to zero, to indicate a good prediction, a value of zero would indicate no difference between

the prediction and the ground truth. The network adjusts its weights gradually to achieve a small loss [34]. The second phase is called **backpropagation** in which the loss is propagated backwards through the network. In this process the perceptrons only receive a fraction of the total loss based on their relative contribution to the output [39]. For further information on the process of backpropagation the article *Understanding Backpropagation* is a good starting point [40]. For adjusting the weights an **optimizer** is used. This is the algorithm changing the weights in small steps to lower the loss. Again there are different algorithms that are used frequently, some popular examples are **gradient descent**, **stochastic gradient descent**, **adam** which is an extension to stochastic gradient descent or **adagrad** [34].

Other terms that should be known for training a model and a better understanding are:

- Epoch: The number of iterations over the whole training dataset while training.
- Batch: The number of samples from the training dataset to process before updating the weights and biases.
- Learning rate: Parameter that provides a scale on how much the weights are to be updated, this is a parameter for the optimizer [41].

3.4.5 Overfitting

While a small loss is the goal, the effect of **overfitting**, where the network learns too detailed features of the training set and can't generalize on new data, is a concern. While training, most models allow a split of the dataset into training and validation data to evaluate performance. There are different approaches to split the dataset and methods like early stopping and data augmentation have also proven to be useful to avoid overfitting. Nevertheless it is advised to set aside a test set for evaluation after the training is finished. To not create a bias it is important, that the network has never seen these examples during training [11].

3.4.6 Evaluation

To determine how the NN is doing there are several quality aspects that can be considered. In chapter 2.4 metrics to measure were introduced, focused on the quality of the segmentation. This is the most commonly used aspect of performance in research at this point [16]. To calculate the metrics a test set has to be prepared. The validation dataset from the training process can't be used for this purpose, since even though the training was not performed directly used for training, the data has been leaked to the network by using this dataset to adjust the parameters, thereby influencing the network. Hence a **test dataset**, which the network has never seen before, is needed [11].

For the evaluation process metrics are chosen depending on the task performed. The values are calculated and presented in the context to describe the performance of the network and make it measurable.

4 DeLTA 2.0

DeLTA 2.0 (Deep Learning for Time-lapse Analysis) is a deep learning-based image processing pipeline for segmenting and tracking cells in time-lapse microscopy video sequences. DeLTA 2.0 is developed by the Dunlop Lab, which is part of the Department of Biomedical Engineering at Boston University, Massachusetts. DeLTA 2.0 is implementing a deep learning segmentation and tracking pipeline for two-dimensional time-lapse analysis of bacteria [14].

DeLTA 2.0 is a U-Net based implementation in TensorFlow 2 [42]. The current version of DeLTA 2.0 is the second published version, which is still actively under development and can be run on CPU or GPU [10].

The Dunlop Lab team is very open for questions regarding DeLTA 2.0 and responds to issues on their gitlab project quickly and in detail. This includes help setting up DeLTA 2.0, solving issues when running the pipeline and creating scripts to run DeLTA 2.0 as answering questions about their workflow to create training data and evaluating the model and about future plans for the project.

While DeLTA 2.0 is still under development and the integration of a graphical user interface (Graphical user interface (GUI)) to correct segmentation and tracking errors is evaluated, at this stage DeLTA 2.0 is not offering a GUI. The workflow is script based, which means that basic skills in neural networks and python programming are needed. The installation process is simplified by offering a conda forge [43,44] for mac OS and Linux or yml configuration file for windows, but still requires some development experience. To get a better understanding of the pipeline, the U-Net Architecture, the first version of DeLTA and the changes made in DeLTA 2.0 are going to be introduced.

4.1 U-Net

U-Net is a CNN architecture designed for image segmentation of biological images that won the ISBI cell tracking challenge 2015 and performs well on different biological segmentation tasks, while having a reasonable training time using GPU. To make full use of the GPU memory a large input tile size and a small batch number of one image per batch is used. A large number of previously seen training images is used to determine the update of the NN [45]. U-Net is considered a breakthrough technology for cell segmentation and can be considered a standard for image analysis tasks [14].

One of the major concerns in the use of deep learning for biological image analysis is the lack of large datasets to train networks on, which limits the success. To solve this problem U-Net makes excessive use of data augmentation by performing elastic deformations to the available training data, hence increasing the existing dataset. Aside from increasing the number of training data, data augmentation offers more value to deep learning as it helps the network to learn invariances, which are common in biological images. In microscopical images often seen invariances are shifts, rotations, deformations and gray value variations, which U-Net simulates by data augmentation. Furthermore data augmentation decreases the possibility of the NN to overfit [45]

Another challenge in cell segmentation is the separation of touching objects of the same class for which U-Net computes a weight map for each ground truth segmentation compensating for pixels of different classes varying in frequency in an image, which is used in the calculation of loss during training [45].

Figure 13: U-Net architecture [45]

The architecture of U-Net is an encoder-decoder network and consists of a contracting path and an almost symmetric expansive path, giving a U-shape. U-Net is using a modified and extended fully convolutional network architecture that is supplemented with successive layers for upsampling, to increase the resolution of the output. One important modification is a large number of feature channels in the upsampling part, to propagate context information to higher resolution layers.

The contracting path is consistent with a typical convolutional network architecture, repeating two 3x3 convolutions, each followed by a ReLU activation function and a 2x2 max pooling layer for downsampling. With every downsampling step, the number of feature channels is doubled. In the upsampling path each upsampling is followed by a 2x2 up-convolution that halves the number of feature channels, a concatenation with the correspondingly cropped feature map from the contracting path and two 3x3 convolutions, each followed by a ReLU. The final layer is a 1x1 convolution to map each 64-component feature vector to the desired number of classes. U-Net consists of 23 convolutional layers in total [45]. For upsampling max-unpooling as described in section 3.3.1 is used [19].

The output of the ReLU functions is used as a skip connection for the corresponding decoder block. A skip connection is a technique which has proven effective to combine different levels of abstractions from different layers to generate sharper segmentation maps by providing additional information [19, 46]. The loss in U-Net is weighted. The computation of the loss is done by a pixel-wise soft-max over the feature map combined with a cross-entropy loss function. The pixel-wise soft-max followed by the cross-entropy classifies each pixel into one of the classes. This conversion is where the segmentation problem is transformed into a classification problem, where each pixel has to belong to a class [45, 47].

4.2 DeLTA

In the paper *DeLTA Automated cell segmentation, tracking, and lineage reconstruction using deep learning* published in 2020, DeLTA was introduced as a framework offering a segmentation and tracking pipeline for time-lapse microscopy. This first version of DeLTA was built for images from mother machine microfluidic devices. The pipeline processes the images by using two U-Net models consecutively. The first model performs the task of segmenting the cells, after which the second model performs tracking and lineage reconstruction as visualized in figure 14 [10].

Figure 14: DeLTA pipeline (A) Schematic representation of mother machine device. (B) Inputs and outputs of the segmentation U-Net. (C) Inputs and outputs of the tracking U-Net (D) Representative kymograph of segmentation and tracking for a single chamber. [10]

This work is focused on the segmentation model and not going into details of the tracking model. The outputs of the segmentation model are used in the tracking model and therefore the accuracy of these outputs is essential for the performance of the subsequent model. To ensure this, the in depth evaluation, retraining and reevaluation are essential.

The segmentation model using the U-Net architecture is similar to the original model using 5 contracting/up-sampling levels. For the training a dataset was generated in a combination of manual work and Ilastik, a software tool for interactive machine learning and bio image analysis [48]. The used model organism for DeLTA is *Escherichia coli* (*E.coli*), a rod shaped bacteria [10]. Like the original U-Net, DeLTA uses data augmentation to make the model robust against overfitting and variations in image conditions. DeLTA implements a pixelwise-weighted cross-entropy, as proposed in [45] in their own implementation, since pixelwise-weighted cross-entropy is not a standard loss function of the used python models. The pixelwise-weighted cross-entropy takes the groundtruth and predicted segmentation map to

calculate the binary pixelwise cross-entropy loss after which an elementwise multiplication of the calculated loss and the weight map. This emphasises the loss in specific areas in order to improve the models performance in these areas [14]. The model was trained over 400 epochs of 250 steps, with a batch size of 10 samples. The results for segmentation presented in the paper show that the segmentation model is doing remarkably well on data looking similar to the training dataset, while having higher error rates when processing different looking images. These results lead to the conclusion that DeLTA works with high accuracy for similar problems without retraining. For differing tasks, where the performance is not sufficient, a retraining with a suitable dataset is expected to get the desired results [10].

Being designed for mother-machine images the first version of DeLTA ignores clustering of cells, which is one of the most problematic parts of image segmentation, where cells touching on possible all sides have to be separated. Since two-dimensional microscopy is an essential tool in biological experiments, DeLTA was developed further released as DeLTA 2.0 [14].

4.3 DeLTA 2.0

DeLTA 2.0: A deep learning pipeline for quantifying single-cell spatial and temporal dynamics, published in 2022, introduces the second version of DeLTA 2.0, a pure Python workflow to analyse images of single-cells on two-dimensional surfaces. While DeLTA 2.0 still supports the analysis of mother-machine images it additionally is able to process two-dimensional images. Two-dimensional environments are more straightforward to implement experimentally, offer the potential to implement co-cultures of cells and can be used to quantify spatial effects and multi-generational phenomena. This type of experiment is often used e.g. to quantify gene expressions and cell growth.

Segmenting and tracking cells in two dimensions is much more challenging than doing the same in mother-machine images. One reason is the growth of the colonies, leading to hundreds of cells in a cluster, where each cell may have neighbors on all sides, making segmentation a difficult task. For the tracking part hundreds of possible assignments have to be considered, since a cell can move in any direction on the two-dimensional surface and move large distances. DeLTA 2.0 is focused on limiting the need for significant user input and post processing, which is often required by other tools for image segmentation and on integrating deep learning for segmentation and tracking into a usable pipeline specific for time-lapse microscopy [14, 49].

The architecture and the pipeline of the original version was kept in DeLTA 2.0 and improvements were implemented. Figure 15 shows the DeLTA 2.0 pipeline.

While in the first version of DeLTA pre- and post-processing in Matlab was necessary, DeLTA 2.0 is purely Python based. Further improvements include the capability to take advantage of the Bio-Formats toolbox for Python. Various input image sizes are accepted, as DeLTA 2.0 will crop larger images into smaller windows for segmentation and stitch the output back together. The data augmentation methods blurring and Gaussian noise addition have been added to the already implemented data augmentation methods to prevent overfitting.

Further improvements are more data recordings while tracking, like pole age.

The weight-maps used in the loss function were customized for DeLTA 2.0 to improve the segmentation of rod-shaped bacteria, increasing the weights for the center of the cells and the borders between the cells. The generation of these weight maps was implemented in

Figure 15: DeLTA 2.0 (A) DeLTA 2.0 pipeline. (B) Segmentation U-Net. (C) Tracking U-Net. (D) Lineage reconstruction. [14]

a function, that can be used to build weight maps for new training data from the ground truth.

The segmentation model was trained for 500 epochs with 300 steps and a batch size of 1.

The code is available on a gitlab repository which is maintained and offers support using the GitLab issue system [50]. Furthermore a documentation is available [51].

4.4 Metrics used to evaluate DeLTA 2.0

In the paper the developers give different evaluations of their network. The computation time for a dataset with additional information about the hardware used, which gives an indication which tasks on which systems might be possible with DeLTA 2.0. DeLTA 2.0 defined own metrics, in which subtle differences between ground truth and prediction were acceptable, regarding segmentation and tracking, i.e. recognizing the exact timepoint of the division of the cell, which is often hard to tell [14]. When asked about their process of generating test data and evaluating the performance of the model they gave detailed insight. The generating of test data was a combination of automated generation of segmentation masks and manual corrections of those masks. When evaluating the performance of segmentation they used the dice coefficient as the main metric, which can be done using a script. And even though parts of the evaluation where done by script, some metrics the team used required manual evaluation. The team was focused on recognizing the borders between cells correctly, which explains the slight under-segmentation of the cells.

5 DeLTA 2.0 Environment

5.1 Installation of DeLTA 2.0

DeLTA 2.0 is purely Python based and it is recommended to run it on GPU for higher performance, though it does run on CPU as well. The tool is platform independent. The requirements to install Delta 2.0 depend on the operating system (OS), the installation is supposed to run on.

For the setup of the pipeline and the planned retraining, the installation was made on a GPU cluster of the MPI (Deepbio). The system runs on Ubuntu 18.04.6 LTS and can be accessed using secure shell (ssh) which is shown in listing 1. The hardware of the GPU cluster consists of an Intel(R) Xeon(R) Silver 4216 CPU @ 2.10GHz CPU, eight NVIDIA(R) GeForce GTX 2080 Ti graphics cards and 386 GB of memory. Data is stored on a network storage. The prerequisites for the installation, described in the documentation, are met on the GPU cluster. For Linux and MacOSX, DeLTA 2.0 is available as conda-forge. The resolving of the environment took unreasonable long and had to be aborted. The documentation already notes this as a common issue and recommends to use mamba, another python package manager which offers better performance than anaconda [52], for the install, which solved the problem. To enable DeLTA 2.0 to process images like .czi files, which are a common file for time-lapse microscopy experiments at the MPI, the python-bioformats library had to be installed additionally [53].

```

1 username@RZ012 MINGW64 ~/Desktop
2 $ ssh username@deepbio
3 username@deepbio's password:
4 Welcome to Ubuntu 18.04.6 LTS (GNU/Linux 4.15.0-193-generic x86_64)
5
6 * Documentation: https://help.ubuntu.com
7 * Management:   https://landscape.canonical.com
8 * Support:      https://ubuntu.com/advantage
9
10 System information as of Thu Oct 6 12:24:44 CEST 2022
11
12 System load: 0.08          Processes:          777
13 Usage of /:  74.9% of 182.28GB  Users logged in:   0
14 Memory usage: 0%          IP address for eno1: 172.16.5.150
15 Swap usage:  0%           IP address for docker0: 172.17.0.1
16
17 * Super-optimized for small spaces - read how we shrank the memory
18   footprint of MicroK8s to make it the smallest full K8s around.
19
20 https://ubuntu.com/blog/microk8s-memory-optimisation
21
22 36 updates can be applied immediately.
23 10 of these updates are standard security updates.
24 To see these additional updates run: apt list --upgradable
25
26
27 Last login: Sat Sep 24 17:50:27 2022 from 172.16.0.13
28 username@deepbio:~$ source /opt/anaconda3/bin/activate
29 (base) username@deepbio:~$ conda activate delta_env
30 (delta_env) username@deepbio:~$ jupyter lab --no-browser --port=10013 --notebook-dir $HOME --ip
   =0.0.0.0
31 [I 2022-10-06 12:27:07.991 ServerApp] jupyterlab | extension was successfully linked.
32 [I 2022-10-06 12:27:14.213 ServerApp] nbclassic | extension was successfully linked.
33 [I 2022-10-06 12:27:14.674 ServerApp] nbclassic | extension was successfully loaded.
34 [I 2022-10-06 12:27:14.675 LabApp] JupyterLab extension loaded from /home/username/.conda/envs/
   delta_env/lib/python3.9/site-packages/jupyterlab
35 [I 2022-10-06 12:27:14.675 LabApp] JupyterLab application directory is /home/username/.conda/envs
   /delta_env/share/jupyter/lab
36 [I 2022-10-06 12:27:14.684 ServerApp] jupyterlab | extension was successfully loaded.
37 [I 2022-10-06 12:27:14.685 ServerApp] Serving notebooks from local directory: /home/username
38 [I 2022-10-06 12:27:14.685 ServerApp] Jupyter Server 1.13.5 is running at:

```

```
39 [I 2022-10-06 12:27:14.685 ServerApp] http://deepbio:10013/lab?token=4225677274
    e8bab8e094305447016adee1e004e7491e3988
40 [I 2022-10-06 12:27:14.685 ServerApp] or http://127.0.0.1:10013/lab?token=4225677274
    e8bab8e094305447016adee1e004e7491e3988
41 [I 2022-10-06 12:27:14.685 ServerApp] Use Control-C to stop this server and shut down all kernels
    (twice to skip confirmation).
42 [C 2022-10-06 12:27:14.713 ServerApp]
43
44 To access the server, open this file in a browser:
45 file:///home/username/.local/share/jupyter/runtime/jpserver-48840-open.html
46 Or copy and paste one of these URLs:
47 http://deepbio:10013/lab?token=4225677274e8bab8e094305447016adee1e004e7491e3988
48 or http://127.0.0.1:10013/lab?token=4225677274e8bab8e094305447016adee1e004e7491e3988
```

Listing 1: Access jupyter lab on GPU cluster

To be able to adjust scripts directly in the environment built for DeLTA 2.0, jupyter lab was installed making it possible to edit jupyter notebooks in a browser as shown in figure 16.

Figure 16: Jupyter Lab on Deepbio.

The folder structure was setup as shown in figure 17.

Figure 17: Structure of provided training dataset 2D

While working on the project some technical issues with the GPU clusters occurred. This made it necessary to install a working environment on a windows machine with a RTX2070 Super. This also made some changes to the scripts necessary. In the following some scripts will have additional imports and code lines which are commented to not be executed. This is to adapt the scripts quickly to the current working environment by comment and uncomment the corresponding lines of code to make the script run. The lines are explained in the comments. The cluster was not reinstalled before finishing the calculations for this project. This limited the processing power and therefore limited the number of experiments that could be run in a given time frame. The cluster is going to be used for further training and Deep Learning image processing in the future.

5.2 DeLTA 2.0 Config files

JSON files are used to store configurations to run DeLTA 2.0. In the config file is used to parameterize operations in the modules. To get started there is a function provided, that downloads example data, creating a preset config file in the process which is shown in listing 2. A config file needs to be loaded prior to execution of any DeLTA 2.0 function. The parameters from the config file can be overwritten on-the-fly in the Python script to be executed [53].

```

1 {
2   "presets": "2D",
3   "models": [
4     "segmentation",
5     "tracking"
6   ],
7   "model_file_rois": "",
8   "model_file_seg": "../assets/delta/models/unet_pads_seg.hdf5",
9   "model_file_track": "../assets/delta/models/unet_pads_track.hdf5",
10  "target_size_rois": [
11    512,
12    512
13  ],
14  "target_size_seg": [

```

```
15     512,
16     512
17 ],
18 "target_size_track": [
19     256,
20     256
21 ],
22 "training_set_rois": "",
23 "training_set_seg": "../assets/delta/trainingsets/2D/training/segmentation_set",
24 "training_set_track": "../assets/delta/trainingsets/2D/training/tracking_set",
25 "eval_movie": "../assets/delta/eval_movies/2D/movie_tifs",
26 "rotation_correction": false,
27 "drift_correction": false,
28 "crop_windows": true,
29 "min_roi_area": 500,
30 "whole_frame_drift": false,
31 "min_cell_area": 20,
32 "save_format": [
33     "pickle",
34     "legacy",
35     "movie"
36 ],
37 "TF_CPP_MIN_LOG_LEVEL": "2",
38 "memory_growth_limit": null,
39 "pipeline_seg_batch": 64,
40 "pipeline_track_batch": 64
41 }
```

Listing 2: DeLTA 2.0 config file example

The configuration files allows adjustment of parameters like which model files and which images are going to be used. Parameters for image sizes and saving formats can be adjusted as parameters with regard to the training parameters batch size. A description of all parameters can be found in the DeLTA 2.0 documentation [51].

The config file created by DeLTA 2.0 uses absolute paths. For portability of this project relative paths were saved in the config files.

5.3 DeLTA 2.0 Assets

DeLTA 2.0 offers assets to get started with the pipeline. The assets can be downloaded by script as in listing 3, including all assets.

```
1 import delta
2
3 delta.assets.download_assets()
```

Listing 3: DeLTA 2.0 assets download.

The function takes parameters to specify, which assets should be downloaded, if not all assets are needed or a different path is preferred. The assets are also available as zip files to download from a google drive folder [53].

The folder contains data to be processed as material to get to know the pipeline, model files of pretrained models and training data for mother machine data and two dimensional data. Figure 18 shows the folder structure of the data, most relevant for our project.

Figure 18: Folder structure DeLTA 2.0 assets download per script

5.4 DeLTA 2.0 Pipeline

Even though this work is focused on the segmentation and the retraining of the segmentation model, it is important to introduce the overall purpose of DeLTA 2.0. The focus on segmentation is rooted in segmentation being the first step of further analysis, hence the quality of the segmentation determines the quality of all further processing. Nevertheless the following analysis is relevant and should be kept in mind. For that reason, I will shortly introduce the DeLTA 2.0 pipeline, which is the core element of DeLTA 2.0.

The DeLTA 2.0 Pipeline is built to analyse a time-lapse producing an output, specified in the config file. Possible outputs from this pipeline are a pickle file, which can be used for reloading corresponding position object, a Matlab file, which is a legacy file from the first version of DeLTA 2.0 and an MP4 movie, that can be used for a fast determination of the quality of the segmentation and tracking results. The input for the pipeline is determined by the *eval_movie* parameter of the config file. The XPreader class of DeLTA 2.0 handles the input and is passed on to the pipeline. If the given path points to a folder, the folder is expected to contain single-page tif files. The XPreader offers a parameter to handle bioformat files, like czi, given that the python-bioformats library is installed [53].

The pipeline runs through different phases:

1. ROI detection, rotation correction and drift correction. This step is optional and usually performed for mother machine chambers.

2. Segmentation of images.
3. Track segmented cells over the timelapse and reconstruct the lineage.
4. Extraction of features.
5. Saving the results.

5.4.1 Running the pipeline

For confirmation of the functionality of the run time environment, a test of the pipeline was conducted. The results of the test gave a first impression of the performance of the segmentation that the pretrained model can perform. For this the assets provided by DeLTA 2.0 were downloaded.

The pretrained model provided was used to run the whole pipeline on the data provided by DeLTA 2.0 and on an image from the MPI dataset. The figure below shows one enlarged frame from the movie created by DeLTA 2.0 and one enlarged image from the movie created from the MPI data.

(a) Pipeline test with data provided by DeLTA 2.0 [14].

(b) Pipeline test with data from the MPI dataset.

Figure 19: DeLTA 2.0 pipeline test.

The images in figure 19 show that even though, the model is separating the objects, the segmentation is smaller than the cell in the microscopy image and the cell is not segmented accurately. As established through conversation with the DeLTA 2.0 development team, the main focus in their training was on detecting the *'borders'* between bacteria cells to ensure correct tracking and lineage reconstruction, which is an important issue for studies. Nonetheless the shrinking of the cells might cause errors in measuring the cell size, which is an important part of the experiments conducted at the MPI. Because of this, we decided to try to improve the segmentation with this project by setting up metrics to evaluate if a retraining can get more accurate results.

6 Data preparation

DeLTA 2.0 relies on supervised training, hence a training dataset has to be created. As a guideline the DeLTA 2.0 dataset is reviewed. To create comparability the dataset created should have the same number of samples and the complexity of the segmentation in the datasets should be similar.

6.1 DeLTA 2.0 training dataset

The dataset provided for DeLTA 2.0 consists of 307 images with variations in image aspects like brightness, contrast, sharpness as well as in aspects of cluster size of the bacteria and even including different shaped bacteria, examples from the DeLTA 2.0 training dataset are shown in figure 20.

Figure 20: Samples from DeLTA 2.0 training set [14].

For each sample a segmentation mask and a weight map as described in chapter 4.3 is provided, as shown in figure 21.

Figure 21: Sample from DeLTA 2.0 with segmentation mask and weight map [14].

The folder structure for the training dataset is shown in figure 22. Images, segmentation masks and weight maps are stored in sibling folders, and each sample with its associated segmentation mask and weight map are given the same file name.

Figure 22: Structure of provided training dataset 2D

All samples of the training dataset show clusters of bacteria. As already described in section 4.3 the segmentation of bacteria cells in clusters, where cells are touching or even overlapping, is a complicated task and the model is more challenged to learn to segment cells in clusters than with learning to segment single cells. The developers of DeLTA 2.0 confirmed this as the reason for the selection of images with large clusters [49].

The images were examined by reviewing their properties upon examining them in Adobe Photoshop. The images provided are PNG files with a bit depth of 24 bit, i.e. 3 channels with each 8 bit, which means the image is an RGB image, even though no color information is stored and a grayscale image would have been sufficient.

(a) Properties of a sample image

(b) Sample image in Photoshop, choosing a small slice for examination with python.

Figure 23: Examination of sample data.

For further investigation a 30 x 20 pixel patch, as shown in figure 23 from an image was examined by reading it with the python opencv library and getting an output of the datatype and the array representation of the image. To illustrate the array representation the part of the image which is represented by the array is added as an overlay in figure 24. For

losing information, but this may lead to problems when running the pipeline. The weight map uses values between 0 and 255 to indicate the importance of the pixel in question for the training process.

```

Channel 1
[[90 91 91 92 92 93 92 93 92 91 92 93 93 93 94 93 97 96 94 96 94 90 92 90 91 90 89 87 85 85]
 [93 93 93 92 92 91 91 92 93 92 93 91 92 92 94 92 95 96 92 94 94 94 94 93 92 90 89 87 89 87]
 [93 94 93 90 92 90 93 90 91 91 91 89 90 92 90 92 92 91 94 93 95 97 97 95 94 92 89 90 88 87]
 [95 93 93 92 89 90 90 90 91 88 87 86 87 88 86 88 90 91 92 93 96 97 98 95 95 92 91 90 87 84]
 [96 93 92 93 91 90 89 88 85 83 81 81 81 82 84 84 88 89 93 95 97 96 97 99 96 94 94 90 89 87]
 [93 91 91 90 90 87 84 79 79 74 73 70 71 71 74 79 82 87 88 91 94 95 97 99 97 95 93 93 91 87]
 [93 92 90 87 86 84 77 74 67 63 58 57 57 59 64 68 75 80 85 91 96 99 99 97 97 98 95 94 91 89]]

Channel 2
[[90 91 91 92 92 93 92 93 92 91 92 93 93 93 94 93 97 96 94 96 94 90 92 90 91 90 89 87 85 85]
 [93 93 93 92 92 91 91 92 93 92 93 91 92 92 94 92 95 96 92 94 94 94 94 93 92 90 89 87 89 87]
 [93 94 93 90 92 90 93 90 91 91 91 89 90 92 90 92 92 91 94 93 95 97 97 95 94 92 89 90 88 87]
 [95 93 93 92 89 90 90 90 91 88 87 86 87 88 86 88 90 91 92 93 96 97 98 95 95 92 91 90 87 84]
 [96 93 92 93 91 90 89 88 85 83 81 81 81 82 84 84 88 89 93 95 97 96 97 99 96 94 94 90 89 87]
 [93 91 91 90 90 87 84 79 79 74 73 70 71 71 74 79 82 87 88 91 94 95 97 99 97 95 93 93 91 87]
 [93 92 90 87 86 84 77 74 67 63 58 57 57 59 64 68 75 80 85 91 96 99 99 97 97 98 95 94 91 89]]

Channel 3
[[90 91 91 92 92 93 92 93 92 91 92 93 93 93 94 93 97 96 94 96 94 90 92 90 91 90 89 87 85 85]
 [93 93 93 92 92 91 91 92 93 92 93 91 92 92 94 92 95 96 92 94 94 94 94 93 92 90 89 87 89 87]
 [93 94 93 90 92 90 93 90 91 91 91 89 90 92 90 92 92 91 94 93 95 97 97 95 94 92 89 90 88 87]
 [95 93 93 92 89 90 90 90 91 88 87 86 87 88 86 88 90 91 92 93 96 97 98 95 95 92 91 90 87 84]
 [96 93 92 93 91 90 89 88 85 83 81 81 81 82 84 84 88 89 93 95 97 96 97 99 96 94 94 90 89 87]
 [93 91 91 90 90 87 84 79 79 74 73 70 71 71 74 79 82 87 88 91 94 95 97 99 97 95 93 93 91 87]
 [93 92 90 87 86 84 77 74 67 63 58 57 57 59 64 68 75 80 85 91 96 99 99 97 97 98 95 94 91 89]]

```

Figure 25: Comparing array representation of all three channels of an image.

As shown in figure 25 all 3 channels store the same value for each pixel, making the information redundant, hence, technically the images could be stored as grayscale images without loss of information, but this could affect the network.

6.2 Creating Training Data

To create training data multiple approaches were examined in preparation for this project as well as in a scientific project which reviewed image segmentation for bacterial cells. Different tools for partial automation of the workflow were evaluated and tested. Some of the tools like Ilastik or the Fiji Plugin MicrobeJ offered various parameter settings to enhance the automated segmentation. With those tools some success could be seen, especially in images with a small number of cells. The more crowded the scene got the less accurate and helpful the tools were [54]. The developers of DeLTA 2.0 confirmed that their workflow included manual correction of their training data set. In this workflow the first 100 samples were created using Ilastik and manual correction of the masks in Adobe Photoshop. With those 100 samples the model was trained and the other samples were created by getting predictions from the model and correcting the predicted masks manually, completing the training dataset and retraining the model with the 307 samples. Also the possibility to get more training samples with other model organisms in it, by using the omnipose dataset [55] in addition to their own was discussed [49].

The manual annotation of the images is a time consuming process which could not be completed by a single person within the time set for the project. To get all the samples

needed in a reasonable time the team [54] helped annotating the data. To establish an efficient workflow each member of the annotation team used a graphic tablet and either Adobe Photoshop or Affinity Photo. Each individual could choose to pre-process the images with MicrobeJ and correct the created masks or to annotate from scratch. The following workflow is the one preferred by the author and just one possible way.

The time-lapse data to be used is stored on an Omero server as czi files. In the first step the czi files had to be split into single images by their timepoints. Initially this was done using Fiji and the Bio-Formats Importer/Exporter as shown in figure 26 [56].

(a) Bioformats Export Fiji.

(b) Timepoint split of czi in Fiji.

Figure 26: Splitting the czi file with Fiji Bio-Formats Exporter.

Since this is a time consuming task that can be automated, a function to split a czi file into its timepoints was implemented, shown in listing 4.

```

104 """
105 splitting a czi file and saving the timelapse in single tif files
106
107 Parameters
108 -----
109 input_path : string
110     filepath to czi file as string
111 -----
112 Returns
113 None
114
115 """
116 def czi_split(input_path):
117     # getting meta data from the image by using the xpreader
118     xpreader = utils.xpreader(input_path, use_bioformats=True)
119     # creating filehandle to handle czi file
120     filehandle = bioformats.ImageReader(input_path)
121     meta = bioformats.get_omexml_metadata(input_path)
122     md = bioformats.OMEXML(meta)
123
124     positions = [p for p in range(xpreader.positions)]

```

```

125 channels = [c for c in range(xpreader.channels)]
126 timepoints = [f for f in range(xpreader.timepoints)]
127 # getting output path to save files to
128 tif_path = output_path(xpreader.filename)
129
130 # splitting the file and save tifs
131 for p, pos in enumerate(positions):
132     for c, cha in enumerate(channels):
133         # check for Channel Name to only save phase contrast channel

```

Listing 4: Splitting czi file into tif images by timepoints

For reusable scripts that can support a DeLTA 2.0 workflow a python package called 'deltahelpers' was created, in which these functions were implemented. The deltahelpers code can be found on Zenodo, a platform to share scientific data [57].

The second step was manual annotation in Adobe Photoshop. For better visual adjustments using the curves tool and adjustments of brightness and contrast were made. For this a copy of the file was saved in which the manual annotation was performed. This image manipulation was automated by using Photoshop Actions. The original timepoint image was only manipulated in cases where multiple clusters were visible, of which one was too blurry to be manually segmented. In this case this cluster was removed from the original and was left out for the segmentation mask. The process is illustrated in figure 27.

Figure 27: Original image, lightened image, created segmentation mask and Action panel Adobe Photoshop.

As established in section 6.1 the segmentation mask only contains the values 0 or 255 and none of the values in between. After the manual editing there are still values in between contained in the image. To get rid of these values, the manually edited mask is converted into a bitmap. For this the image has to be down sampled to 8 bits per channel, the bit depth determines how many values can be stored per channel.

(a) Menu for image conversion in Photoshop.

(b) Action in Photoshop.

Figure 28: Image conversion in Adobe Photoshop.

Like before the conversion was partly automated by Photoshop Actions as shown in figure 28.

Looking at the array representation of the images through conversion in figure 29 illustrates the process. The bit depth of 16 bit has a value range from 0 to 65535. To create the bitmap, the image needs to be down sampled to 8 bit with a value range from 0 to 255. The conversion to bitmap ensures that only the values 0 and 255 are left in the array, which is a requirement for the mask, where the value 255 represents the label 'is cell' and the value 0 represents the label 'is not cell'. There are several techniques to convert an image to bitmap, one commonly used is to set a threshold and values are converted to 0 or 255 depending on the fact if they are under or over the threshold.

crowded scenes could take up to an hour to be completely segmented.

Besides converting the file format a naming convention has to be established. Even though the network is not concerned with how the file is named the filenames need to be consistent, i.e. for training each image and the associated segmentation mask and weight map have to be named the same. Since the weight maps are created with a script, we only have to take care of the images and segmentation masks.

The Code snippets in listings 5 and 6 are extracted from the `trainGenerator_seg` function of `data.py` in DeLTA 2.0 implementation. They show that the filenames are used for referencing the images and masks.

```

512 def trainGenerator_seg(
513     batch_size: int,
514     img_path: str,
515     mask_path: str,
516     weight_path: Optional[str],
517     target_size: Tuple[int, int] = (256, 32),
518     augment_params: Dict[str, Any] = {},
519     preload: bool = False,
520     seed: int = 1,
521     crop_windows: bool = False,
522 ) -> Iterator[Tuple[npt.NDArray[np.float32], npt.NDArray[np.float32]]]:

```

Listing 5: Definition of `trainGenerator_seg`.

```

555 # Get training image files list:
556 image_name_arr = glob.glob(os.path.join(img_path, "*.png")) + glob.glob(
557     os.path.join(img_path, "*.tif")
558 )

```

Listing 6: Referencing images by filename.

For making sure each image of the MPI dataset is identifiable the file name needs to implement an id, for cross-referencing we use the id given by the MPI omero server the timelapses are stored on. Furthermore the scene, or position, the channel and timepoint, or frame, need to be identifiable, creating the naming convention seen in listing 7.

```

filename = '{omero_id}_pos{position:02d}cha{channel:02d}fra{frame:06d}'.format(omero_id=id,
    position=p, channel=c, frame=t)

```

Listing 7: Naming convention for MPI training dataset.

The count of position, channel and frame start at zero, as is typical in programming structures. Since DeLTA 2.0 only uses the phase contrast channel, this part of the image split is ignored and only included in the naming of the images to clarify that images can include multiple channels which might be considered for other tools. When creating the data set a different naming convention was used, partly this is due to the automates naming of the Fiji timepoint split. The naming followed the convention shown in listing 8.

```

filename = '{omero_id}_s{position:02d}_T{frame:02d}'.format(omero_id=id, position=p, frame=t)

```

Listing 8: Initial naming convention.

To rename the files the python script shown in listing 9 was used. Since this script can only be used to rename files from a certain pattern to another and is not generalized, it is not supporting a general workflow. For this reason this script part is saved separately and executed locally and not implemented in the `deltahelpers` package.

```
1 import os
2 import glob
3 import re
4
5 temp = sorted(
6     glob.glob('seg/*.tif') + glob.glob('img/*.tif') + glob.glob('seg/*.tiff') + glob.glob('img/*
7     tif')
8 )
9 pattern = re.compile(r'[a-zA-Z]+\\[0-9\]+_s[0-9]+_T[0-9]+\.tif')
10 images = []
11 for t in temp:
12     if pattern.match(t):
13         images.append(t)
14
15 for i in images:
16     old_name = os.path.abspath(i)
17     folder = os.path.abspath(os.path.dirname(i))
18     identifier = re.findall("\d+", i)
19     omero_id = identifier[0]
20     position = '0' + str(int(identifier[1]) - 1)
21     channel = '00'
22     frame = '0000' + identifier[2]
23     new_name = os.path.join(folder, omero_id + '_pos' + position + 'cha' + channel + 'fra' + frame
24     + '.tif')
25     os.rename(old_name, new_name)
```

Listing 9: Renaming images.

As mentioned above the used file format is tif. Initially the images were to be converted to png files for the retraining, since the DeLTA 2.0 dataset is provided as png. While still in the process of creating the dataset a problem with the png format and the creating of the weight maps was discovered, which is going to be explained in detail in section 6.2.3. Tif and png are file formats using lossless compression [23] and could be used interchangeably. For direct comparison we decided to use the same file format to train both models, hence the DeLTA 2.0 data set needs to be converted. For the conversion the python script in listing 10 was written.

```
1 """
2 converting .png or .tiff to .tif
3
4 Parameters
5 -----
6 string: folder
7 -----
8 Returns
9 None
10
11 """
12 def png_to_tif(folder):
13     folder = Path(folder)
14     folder = os.path.abspath(folder)
15     images = sorted(
16         glob.glob(folder + "/*.tiff") + glob.glob(folder + "/*.png")
17     )
18     for image in images:
19         image_name = Path(image).stem
20         img = cv2.imread(image)
21         cv2.imwrite(os.path.join(folder, image_name + '.tif'), img)
```

Listing 10: Function for converting png to tif.

6.2.1 Choosing samples

The DeLTA 2.0 training dataset, which can be downloaded as assets, contains 307 images at this point. For comparability the training dataset should have the same number of sam-

ples. The MPI dataset selected for this project consists of multiple timelines from which all timepoint images where the cells were sharp enough and did not overlap too much were used to create ground truth masks, as described in chapter 6.2. For training the segmentation network it is not necessary to use timelines, since the segmentation network performs semantic segmentation, there is no identification of the time aspect. The DeLTA 2.0 dataset does contain images belonging to timelines, but focuses on images containing cluster of cells. This is due to the fact that segmentation in crowded scenes is harder to learn for the network, just as it is harder for a human to segment these images. To create datasets though, it can help in the manual segmentation process to segment the cells in a cluster, if it is possible to review images on an earlier and later timepoint. The training data has to represent the data the network should handle later. The initial idea was to skip early timepoints with only a few cells for the training dataset. The time consuming process of segmenting images with large clusters and the time restriction of the project made it necessary to adapt this to use the early timepoints in the training dataset as well.

The images in figure 30 show example masks of the DeLTA 2.0 training dataset in comparison to the MPI training dataset. It can be seen, that the borders in the DeLTA 2.0 dataset are broader, which means the cells have not been segmented accurately, the segmentation mask being smaller than the cell in the original image.

(a) DeLTA 2.0 training sample mask with small cell count per cluster [14].

(b) MPI training sample mask with small cell count per cluster.

Figure 30: Masks of low complexity of the datasets.

In the more complex example in figure 31 with clusters including more cells the smaller segmentation masks of the cells and broader borders in the DeLTA 2.0 sample are clearly visible too.

(a) DeLTA 2.0 training sample mask with large cell count per cluster [14].

(b) MPI training sample mask with large cell count per cluster.

Figure 31: Masks of high complexity of the datasets.

A comparison over the whole dataset shows that there are fewer images of low complexity and the dataset is focused to have images with clusters of cells. While the MPI dataset mostly includes images with multiple clusters growing the DeLTA 2.0 dataset does include more images showing a single cell cluster, which makes some of the images in the MPI dataset more complex than most images in the DeLTA 2.0 dataset. In conclusion it can be said, that the MPI dataset is a little less complex with regard to large cell clusters.

6.2.2 Splitting the dataset

As described in section 3.4.6 the dataset is split into a training set, a validation set, and a test set. The split of training and validation is made by the model in the training process. For the test dataset it is essential that the network never sees this data in the training process, therefore we selected the samples for the test set before starting the training and set these samples aside. A typical split for deep learning is 60% for the training data, 20% for the validation data and 20% for the test data [11]. To not limit the samples to train on, our test dataset is going to consist of 57 samples, which is 18,57% of our dataset and leaves 250 samples for training and validation datasets.

The DeLTA 2.0 dataset contains images of different timelines and colonies. Most of the images contain clusters of bacteria cells and only parts of timelines are used. Since not only the metrics of a single image might be interesting, but also how the metrics develop with increase of numbers of cells in a timeline, for the test set, one of those partial timelines with 9 images is chosen. The remaining 48 images for the test set are drawn at regular intervals from the remaining data.

At the point of the data selection 336 images from 6 timelapses, 27 scenes, created by the MPI were annotated. Initially it was decided, that the first images of each timeline should be skipped to mirror the complexity of the DeLTA 2.0 dataset. The time consuming process of generating these complex annotations did prevent this at this point. Only the first image

of 25 of the timelines and the first two images of 2 of the scenes could be left out of the dataset. This leaves 307 images, the same number of images as in the DeLTA 2.0 dataset. For the test dataset like in the DeLTA 2.0 dataset 57 images are selected, in this case the 57 images belong to 6 scenes, which allows us to gain more insight how the segmentation metrics develop when cell numbers increase.

6.2.3 Creating weight Maps

DeLTA 2.0 implements a function to create the weight maps which definition is shown in listing 11.

```
1 def seg_weights_2D(
2     mask: utils.SegmentationMask, classweights: Tuple[int, int] = (1, 1)
3 ) -> npt.NDArray[np.float32]:
```

Listing 11: Definition of `delta.data.seg_weights_2D`

The function takes the segmentation mask and a tuple of class weights to apply to cells and border, per default (1,1) as parameters. The function transforms the given segmentation mask by eroding each cell to a 'skeleton' and deleting all pixels belonging to the cell except for the border pixels. By measuring the distances between the skeletons and the borders a gradient towards the skeleton is calculated which is used for the weight calculation. The comments in the `seg_weights` function for mother machine data notes, that the function runs slow and is best to be executed before beginning to train. Assuming the same is applying for `seg_weights_2D`, the weight maps are going to be created beforehand. This also gives us the opportunity to review the weight maps.

The DeLTA 2.0 dataset already provides generated weight maps. Nonetheless we decided to not convert those png files and instead re-generate them. This allows us to control our process by comparing the newly generated weight maps with the provided ones to ensure our result is beneficial for the training. The `seg_weights_2D` function returns an array with float32 values, a saving of the weight map is not implemented. To save the weight maps the function in listing 12 was implemented in the `deltahelpers` package.

```
206 """
207 saving weight maps for a new training data set for segmentation.
208
209 Parameters
210 -----
211 None
212 -----
213 Returns
214 None
215
216 """
217 def save_seg_weightmaps():
218     seg_folder = os.path.abspath(os.path.join(get_inputs_folder(cfg.training_set_seg), 'seg'))
219     wei_folder = os.path.abspath(os.path.join(get_inputs_folder(cfg.training_set_seg), 'wei'))
220     images = sorted(
221         glob.glob(seg_folder + "/*.tif")
222     )
223     for image in images:
224         image = os.path.basename(image)
225         img = cv2.imread(os.path.join(seg_folder, image))
226         imgarray = np.array(img)
227         wei = seg_weights_2D(imgarray)
228         cv2.imwrite(os.path.join(wei_folder, image), n_wei)
```

Listing 12: Function to save weight maps.

The function was run by the script in listing 13 from a jupyter lab, so the folder can be adjusted by loading a different configuration file.

```

1 """
2 Script to save weight maps using delta.data.seg_weights_2D() and deltahelpers.helpers.
   save_seg_weightmaps()
3
4 @author: bgericke
5 """
6 # sys.path.append only for local execution on windows machine
7 import sys
8 sys.path.append('../delta-dev')
9 # surpress warnings
10 import warnings
11 warnings.filterwarnings('ignore')
12
13 # if not on a windows machine, but on the GPU cluster delete the imports above and uncomment the
   sys import below
14 #import sys
15 import numpy as np
16 from delta.utilities import cfg
17 import os
18
19 sys.path.append('../deltahelpers')
20 from deltahelpers import helpers
21
22 # if on GPU cluster uncomment choice of GPU and select a GPU to run the script on
23 #os.environ['CUDA_VISIBLE_DEVICES']='0'
24
25 # choose configuration file
26 cfg.load_config('../config/mpi_training.json')
27
28 #save weight maps
29 helpers.save_seg_weightmaps()

```

Listing 13: Script to run the creation of weight maps.

When saving a float32 array as a png image with the opencv library, the values are not normalized correctly and the resulting image is not the same as the weight map provided as shown in figure 32.

(a) By DeLTA 2.0 provided weight map sample.

(b) Generated weight map.

Figure 32: File format png, provided weight map and generated weight map.

The array representation in figure 33 helps to investigate the value differences, which might

(a) Array representation DeLTA 2.0 weight map.

(b) Array representation generated weight map 32-bit float.

Figure 35: Array representation weight maps.

The generated weight map is saved as a 32-bit float file. This leads to a different visual and might affect the training process, requiring to the implementation of a normalization of the values before saving the weight map, shown in line 229 of listing 14.

```

206 """
207 saving weight maps for a new training data set for segmentation.
208
209 Parameters
210 -----
211 None
212 -----
213 Returns
214 None
215
216 """
217 def save_seg_weightmaps():
218     seg_folder = os.path.abspath(os.path.join(get_inputs_folder(cfg.training_set_seg), 'seg'))
219     wei_folder = os.path.abspath(os.path.join(get_inputs_folder(cfg.training_set_seg), 'wei'))
220     images = sorted(
221         glob.glob(seg_folder + "/*.tif")
222     )
223     for image in images:
224         image = os.path.basename(image)
225         img = cv2.imread(os.path.join(seg_folder, image))
226         imgarray = np.array(img)
227         wei = seg_weights_2D(imgarray)
228         # normalizing the values to uint8
229         n_wei = cv2.normalize(wei, None, 0, 255, cv2.NORM_MINMAX, cv2.CV_8U)
230         cv2.imwrite(os.path.join(wei_folder, image), n_wei)
    
```

Listing 14: Function to save weight maps with normalization.

The results of running the generation of weight maps with the normalization can be seen in figure 36.

7 Training and predictions

The goal of this project is to improve the performance of the segmentation model by training the network with the MPI dataset. To measure improvements of the model trained with the MPI dataset another model for comparison is needed. Even though the DeLTA 2.0 assets include pretrained models, we decided to retrain a model with the DeLTA 2.0 training data for mainly two reasons.

- The pretrained models are assumed to have used the whole training dataset of 307 images for the training and we wanted to do a test split on this dataset to calculate metrics on.
- By retraining the model we ensure that both models are trained with the same parameters, more so the models are trained using the same environment, i.e. the same version of DeLTA 2.0, and the same hardware resources.

7.1 Training the models

DeLTA 2.0 offers a prepared script to retrain the segmentation model.

```
1 """
2 This script trains the cell segmentation U-Net
3
4 @author: jblugagne
5 @edited: bgericke
6 """
7
8 # sys.path.append only for local execution on windows machine
9 import sys
10 sys.path.append('../delta-dev')
11 # surpress warnings
12 import warnings
13 warnings.filterwarnings('ignore')
14
15 import os
16 import glob
17
18 from tensorflow.keras.callbacks import ModelCheckpoint, EarlyStopping
19
20 from delta.utilities import cfg
21 from delta.model import unet_seg
22 from delta.data import trainGenerator_seg
23
24 # Load config:
25 cfg.load_config('../config/delta_retraining.json')
26
27 # if on GPU cluster uncomment choice of GPU and select a GPU to run the script on
28 #os.environ['CUDA_VISIBLE_DEVICES']='0'
29
30 # Files:
31 training_set = os.path.abspath(cfg.training_set_seg)
32 savefile = os.path.abspath(cfg.model_file_seg)
33
34 # Training parameters:
35 batch_size = 1
36 epochs = 600
37 steps_per_epoch = 300
38 patience = 50
39
40 # Data generator parameters:
41 data_gen_args = dict(
42     rotation=2,
43     rotations_90d=True,
44     zoom=0.15,
45     horizontal_flip=True,
46     vertical_flip=True,
```

```
47 illumination_voodoo=True,
48 gaussian_noise=0.03,
49 gaussian_blur=1,
50 )
51
52 # Generator init:
53 myGene = trainGenerator_seg(
54     batch_size,
55     os.path.abspath(os.path.join(training_set, "img")),
56     os.path.abspath(os.path.join(training_set, "seg")),
57     os.path.abspath(os.path.join(training_set, "wei")),
58     augment_params=data_gen_args,
59     target_size=cfg.target_size_seg,
60     crop_windows=cfg.crop_windows,
61 )
62
63 # Define model:
64 model = unet_seg(input_size=cfg.target_size_seg + (1,))
65 model.summary()
66
67 # Callbacks:
68 model_checkpoint = ModelCheckpoint(
69     savefile, monitor="loss", verbose=2, save_best_only=True
70 )
71 early_stopping = EarlyStopping(monitor="loss", mode="min", verbose=2, patience=patience)
72
73 # Train:
74 history = model.fit(
75     myGene,
76     steps_per_epoch=steps_per_epoch,
77     epochs=epochs,
78     callbacks=[model_checkpoint, early_stopping],
79 )
```

Listing 16: Script to run the creation of weight maps.

The script is setting training parameters which can be set in the configuration file or directly in the training script like in listing 16, lines 34 to 38. In addition to these parameters the *trainGenerator_seg* takes parameters for data augmentation while training the model. These augmentation parameters have to be defined as a dictionary in the script like in listing 16 lines 40 to 50.

The model is a U-Net architecture as described in chapter 4. The DeLTA 2.0 implementation is defined in *delta.model.unet_seg* and *delta.model.unet*, where *delta.model.unet* is called by *delta.model.unet_seg*. The function takes 3 parameters, pretrained weights, input size of the images and levels of the U-Net. Other parameters are hard coded into *delta.model* shown in listing 17. The activation function is defined in *delta.model.unet* as ReLU which was introduced in chapter 3.1.2. The initial weights for each layer are set by *he_normal* which takes a sample from a truncated normal distribution which is the probability distribution derived from that of a normally distributed random variable by bounding the random variable from either below, above or both.

```
246 # Default conv2d parameters:
247 conv2d_parameters = {
248     "activation": "relu",
249     "padding": "same",
250     "kernel_initializer": "he_normal",
251 }
```

Listing 17: Model parameters hard coded in DeLTA 2.0.

The final activation, optimizer, the loss function developed by the DeLTA development team and metrics are defined in *delta.model.unet_seg* shown in listing 18.

```
435 model = unet(  
436     input_size=input_size,  
437     final_activation="sigmoid",  
438     output_classes=1,  
439     levels=levels,  
440 )  
441  
442 model.compile(  
443     optimizer=Adam(learning_rate=1e-4),  
444     loss=pixelwise_weighted_binary_crossentropy_seg,  
445     metrics=[unstack_acc],  
446 )
```

Listing 18: Model definition and initialization.

To make adjustments to those parameters an own implementation of the model would have to be made. As describe in section 3 and section 4, the chosen parameters have proven to be effective in image processing tasks and the loss function has been especially designed for image segmentation of bacteria in microscopy images. Therefore the parameters are going to be adopted at this point.

7.1.1 Training process

The model implements **early stopping** which is a technique to prevent overfitting and stops the model when the loss keeps dropping, but the validation error is starting to increase again instead of dropping further [11]. Hence the model does not train for the 600 epochs that were set in the configuration. Training the model with this configuration with the DeLTA 2.0 dataset started with a loss of 191.9152 and stopped after 314 epochs when the training loss did not improve from 16.84551 in epoch 264 the training continued for 50 epochs as set in the patience parameter and when no further improvement was made stopped with the weights saved from epoch 264. Training the model with this configuration with the MPI dataset the training started with a loss of 69.2302 and converged after 133 epochs when the training loss did not improve from 4.01674 in epoch 83. The considerable difference between the number of epochs and the loss did raise some concern. The loss of the first epoch with the initial weights already had a considerable difference, DeLTA 2.0 training loss in the first epoch 191.9152 and MPI training loss in the first epoch 69.2302. This can be caused by the initial setting of the weights, the complexity of the dataset or an error in the training itself. To validate the training process and the resulting models the training was repeated. The plot in figure 40 shows the loss during training while figure 41 shows the accuracy during training.

Figure 40: Loss while training the models.

Figure 41: Accuracy while training the models.

The second training run still shows a significant difference but it also shows that there is a certain randomness and that the initial weights do affect how many epochs the training requires. Whether or not other factors might have caused the differences cannot be determined at this point and the predictions on the images of the test sets and the evaluation of those predictions might give more insights. For the next step the models of the second training run were used.

7.2 Making predictions

Per default when running the DeLTA 2.0 pipeline the segmentation masks are not saved. For our purpose the predicted masks are needed to be compared to the ground truth. The DeLTA 2.0 data module implements a function to save the predicted segmentation masks; the definition of the function is shown in listing 19.

```

663 def saveResult_seg(
664     save_path: str,
665     npyfile: np.ndarray,
666     files_list: List[str] = [],
667     multipage: bool = False,
668 ):
669     """
670     Saves an array of segmentation output images to disk
671
672     Parameters
673     -----
674     save_path : string
675         Path to save folder.
676     npyfile : 3D or 4D numpy array
677         Array of segmentation outputs to save to individual files. If 4D, only
678         the images from the first index of axis=3 will be saved.
679     files_list : list of strings, optional
680         Filenames to save the segmentation masks as. png, tif or jpg extensions
681         work.
682         The default is [].
683     multipage : bool, optional
684         Flag to save all output masks as a single, multi-page TIFF file. Note
685         that if the file already exists, the masks will be appended to it.
686         The default is False.
687
688     Returns
689     -----
690     None.
691
692     """

```

Listing 19: Definition of the function to save predicted masks.

The script shown in listing 20 provided to make use of `delta.data.saveResult_track()` is provided on the DeLTA 2.0 gitlab repository.

```

1  """
2  This script runs the segmentation U-Net
3  For mother machine data, it runs on images of cropped out and resized single
4  chambers as fed to it in Pipeline processing.
5
6  The images are processed by batches of 4096 to prevent memory issues.
7
8  @author: jblugagne
9  """
10
11 import os
12 import glob
13
14 import numpy as np
15
16 from delta.data import saveResult_seg, predictGenerator_seg, postprocess, readreshape
17 from delta.model import unet_seg
18 import delta.utilities as utils
19 from delta.utilities import cfg
20
21 # Load config:
22 cfg.load_config(presets="2D")
23
24 # Input image sequence (change to whatever images sequence you want to evaluate):
25 inputs_folder = cfg.eval_movie
26
27 # # For mother machine instead:

```

```

28 # cfg.load_config(presets='mothermachine')
29
30 # # Images sequence (change to whatever images sequence you want to evaluate):
31 # inputs_folder = os.path.join(cfg.eval_movie, 'cropped_rois')
32
33 # Outputs folder:
34 outputs_folder = os.path.join(inputs_folder, "segmentation")
35 if not os.path.exists(outputs_folder):
36     os.makedirs(outputs_folder)
37
38 # List files in inputs folder:
39 unprocessed = sorted(
40     glob.glob(inputs_folder + "/*.tif") + glob.glob(inputs_folder + "/*.png")
41 )
42
43 # Load up model:
44 model = unet_seg(input_size=cfg.target_size_seg + (1,))
45 model.load_weights(cfg.model_file_seg)
46
47 # Process
48 while unprocessed:
49     # Pop out filenames
50     ps = min(4096, len(unprocessed)) # 4096 at a time
51     to_process = unprocessed[0:ps]
52     del unprocessed[0:ps]
53
54     # Input data generator:
55     predGene = predictGenerator_seg(
56         inputs_folder,
57         files_list=to_process,
58         target_size=cfg.target_size_seg,
59         crop=cfg.crop_windows,
60     )
61
62     # mother machine: Don't crop images into windows
63     if not cfg.crop_windows:
64         # Predictions:
65         results = model.predict(predGene, verbose=1)[: , : , : , 0]
66
67     # 2D: Cut into overlapping windows
68     else:
69         img = readreshape(
70             os.path.join(inputs_folder, to_process[0]),
71             target_size=cfg.target_size_seg,
72             crop=True,
73         )
74         # Create array to store predictions
75         results = np.zeros((len(to_process), img.shape[0], img.shape[1], 1))
76         # Crop, segment, stitch and store predictions in results
77         for i in range(len(to_process)):
78             # Crop each frame into overlapping windows:
79             windows, loc_y, loc_x = utils.create_windows(
80                 next(predGene)[0, :, :], target_size=cfg.target_size_seg
81             )
82             # We have to play around with tensor dimensions to conform to
83             # tensorflow's functions:
84             windows = windows[:, :, :, np.newaxis]
85             # Predictions:
86             pred = model.predict(windows, verbose=1, steps=windows.shape[0])
87             # Stich prediction frames back together:
88             pred = utils.stitch_pic(pred[:, :, :, 0], loc_y, loc_x)
89             pred = pred[np.newaxis, :, :, np.newaxis] # Mess around with dims
90
91             results[i] = pred
92
93     # Post process results (binarize + light morphology-based cleaning):
94     results = postprocess(results, crop=cfg.crop_windows)
95
96     # Save to disk:
97     saveResult_seg(outputs_folder, results, files_list=to_process)

```

Listing 20: Script to use the function to save predicted segmentation masks.

For re-usability the script was implemented into the deltahelpers package.

7.2.1 Saving predicted segmentation masks

The provided script in listing 20 for saving the predicted segmentation masks has several drawbacks when saving the predictions for the test split of the DeLTA 2.0 training dataset. The DeLTA 2.0 training dataset contains images of various dimensions which cannot be processed in one run of the script due to an error caused by the different dimensions shown in listing 24.

```
ValueError: could not broadcast input array from shape (2048,2048,1) into shape (520,696,1)
Trying to adapt the script to process each image by itself did not succeed.
```

Listing 21: Value error when running the script in listing 20 on images with different dimensions.

Another issue is that the script cannot handle a single image and the selected test set did have image dimensions only represented by a single image. Trying to run the script on a folder containing only one image caused an error in the DeLTA 2.0 code shown in listing 22.

```
IndexError                                Traceback (most recent call last)
~\AppData\Local\Temp\ipykernel_14172\2019690402.py in <module>
----> 1 helpers.save_masks()

~\Documents\DeLTA\scripts\deltahelpers\helpers.py in save_masks()
    202
    203     # Save to disk:
--> 204     saveResult_seg(outputs_folder, results, files_list=to_process)
    205
    206 """

~\Documents\DeLTA\scripts\..\delta-dev\delta\data.py in saveResult_seg(save_path, npyfile,
    files_list, multipage)
    704     else:
    705         if files_list:
--> 706             filename = os.path.join(save_path, os.path.basename(files_list[i]))
    707         else:
    708             filename = os.path.join(save_path, "%d_predict.png" % i)

IndexError: list index out of range
```

Listing 22: Index error when running script from listing 20 on a single image.

An attempt to adapt the script to run the creation of the predictions on each image in a folder separately was made which can be seen in listing 23.

```
62 # mother machine: Don't crop images into windows
63 if not cfg.crop_windows:
64     # Predictions:
65     results = model.predict(predGene, verbose=1)[: , : , : , 0]
66
67 # 2D: Cut into overlapping windows
68 else:
69     # Create array to store predictions
70
71     #results = np.zeros((len(to_process), img.shape[0], img.shape[1], 1))
72     # Crop, segment, stitch and store predictions in results
73
74     for i in range(len(to_process)):
75         img = readreshape(
76             os.path.join(inputs_folder, to_process[i]),
77             target_size=cfg.target_size_seg,
78             crop=True,
79         )
80         naming = to_process[i]
81         img_arr = np.zeros((1, img.shape[0], img.shape[1], 1))
```

```
82 # Crop each frame into overlapping windows:
83 windows, loc_y, loc_x = utils.create_windows(
84     next(predGene)[0, :, :], target_size=cfg.target_size_seg
85 )
86 # We have to play around with tensor dimensions to conform to
87 # tensorflow's functions:
88 windows = windows[:, :, :, np.newaxis]
89 # Predictions:
90 pred = model.predict(windows, verbose=1, steps=windows.shape[0])
91 # Stich prediction frames back together:
92 pred = utils.stitch_pic(pred[:, :, :, 0], loc_y, loc_x)
93 pred = pred[np.newaxis, :, :, np.newaxis] # Mess around with dims
94 img_arr = pred
95 print(img_arr)
96 print(img_arr.shape)
97 img_arr = postprocess(img_arr, crop=cfg.crop_windows)
98 saveResult_seg(outputs_folder, img_arr, files_list=naming)
```

Listing 23: Try to adapt the script to create prediction segmentation maps.

While this did solve the previous errors, it resulted in another error with regard to the array representation of the image shown in listing 24.

```
ValueError: Image must be 2D (grayscale, RGB, or RGBA).
```

Listing 24: Value error when running the changed script in listing 23.

Since a script change to solve the problem at hand proved to be time consuming and only affected the processing of this specific dataset, the DeLTA 2.0 test set was sorted by dimensions and the script was run on each subset. For subsets only containing a single image a copy of the image was created, the script was run and the copy of the image and the associated mask were deleted. This procedure was done for a prediction by the model trained on the DeLTA 2.0 dataset. For two of the images the predicted segmentation masks did not match the dimensions. For example for an image with the dimensions 500px x 500px a segmentation mask of 512px x 512px was created. Since this only applied to two images, these two masks were sliced in Photoshop to match the dimensions which was possible, since the additional pixels were added at the end the x and y axis.

The prediction for the MPI test dataset was less complicated, since all the images are of the same dimensions. Predictions by the model trained with the DeLTA 2.0 dataset and a predictions by the model trained with the MPI dataset were generated.

8 Evaluation

To evaluate the performance of the model retrained with the prepared MPI training dataset 4 sets of predictions were generated.

	DeLTA 2.0 test set	MPI test set
DeLTA 2.0 model	prediction set 1	prediction set 2
MPI model	prediction set 3	prediction set 4

Table 1: Generated sets of predicted segmentation masks..

8.1 Choice of Metrics

In section 2.4 different metrics were introduced. To evaluate the performance of the trained models the pixel accuracy and IoU were calculated. The metrics were calculated as average over all test images, for each prediction separately and for images of a timeline to see the development of the metrics when a scene is getting more crowded.

For the calculation of the metrics the python package scikit-learn was used, specific the functions `metrics.accuracy_score` and `metrics.jaccard_score`. Both functions return a value between 0 and 1, where 1 indicates perfect match between predictions and ground truth in the evaluation, see section 2.4.1 and section 2.4.2 as well as reference [59].

For processing the calculations the function shown in listing 25 was implemented to calculate the metrics and return them in an easy to analyse data format.

```

19 """
20 Calculating metrics
21
22 Parameters
23 -----
24 save_location : Path
25   Path to folder/ file from config
26 -----
27 Returns
28 df : dataframe with the metrics
29 Path to save the output data to
30
31 """
32 def calculate_metrics(config_path):
33     config_path = Path(config_path)
34     # getting ground truth and predictions path DeLTA test set
35     gt_path = os.path.abspath(os.path.join(config_path, '../seg'))
36     pred_deltamodel = os.path.abspath(os.path.join(gt_path, '../predictions/
37         predicted_with_delta_train'))
38     pred_mpimodel = os.path.abspath(os.path.join(gt_path, '../predictions/
39         predicted_with_mpi_train'))
40
41     files = [os.path.basename(x) for x in glob.glob(gt_path + "/*.tif")]
42     df = pd.DataFrame(
43         columns=['Accuracy prediction with DeLTA', 'Accuracy prediction with MPI', 'IoU prediction
44             with DeLTA',
45             'IoU prediction with MPI'], index=files)
46
47     for filename in files:
48         gt = os.path.join(gt_path, filename)
49         pred_delta = os.path.join(pred_deltamodel, filename)
50         pred_mpi = os.path.join(pred_mpimodel, filename)
51         groundtruth = cv2.imread(gt, cv2.IMREAD_GRAYSCALE)
52         p_delta = cv2.imread(pred_delta, cv2.IMREAD_GRAYSCALE)

```

```
50 p_mpi = cv2.imread(pred_mpi, cv2.IMREAD_GRAYSCALE)
51
52 acc_delta = metrics.accuracy_score(groundtruth, p_delta)
53 acc_mpi = metrics.accuracy_score(groundtruth, p_mpi)
54 jac_delta = metrics.jaccard_score(groundtruth, p_delta, average='weighted')
55 jac_mpi = metrics.jaccard_score(groundtruth, p_mpi, average='weighted')
56 df.loc[filename] = pd.Series(
57     {'Accuracy prediction with DeLTA': acc_delta, 'Accuracy prediction with MPI': acc_mpi,
58      'IoU prediction with DeLTA': jac_delta, 'IoU prediction with MPI': jac_mpi})
59
60 return df
```

Listing 25: Function to calculate metrics and preprocess.

The requirement to run the function is that the groundtruth segmentation masks are only containing the values 0 and 255 and no values in between, otherwise the functions for calculating the metrics cannot handle the input. Hence the conversion to bitmap and back to grayscale in section 6.2 is an essential pre-processing step to prevent the script to terminate with an error. Some of the images of the DeLTA 2.0 dataset were not pre-processed properly. After these images were converted to bitmap and back to grayscale the script could be run.

Returning the metrics in a dataframe, using the python module pandas [60], which allows evaluation of the data with pandas functions, e.g. the export to csv files or getting the average values. Since the function in listing 25 is not directly supporting the DeLTA 2.0 workflow and is not completely generalized and the folder structure is still partly hard coded, it was not implemented in `deltahelpers.helpers`. Since the script needed to be run unchanged for two scenarios and the function was outsourced to `deltahelpers.evalmetrics` for that purpose. This decision was made with further development in mind.

Results for evaluation metrics are given in the next section.

9 Results

The metrics for every single image of the DeLTA 2.0 test set can be found in *deta_eval.csv* and the metrics for every single image of the MPI test set can be found in *mpi_eval.csv* in the file attachment of this thesis [57]. The average accuracy is shown in table 2, the average IoU is shown in table 3.

	DeLTA 2.0 test set	MPI test set
DeLTA 2.0 model	0.530915	0.784308
MPI model	0.494392	0.785122

Table 2: Average accuracy for predicted segmentation masks.

	DeLTA 2.0 test set	MPI test set
DeLTA 2.0 model	0.798261	0.603633
MPI model	0.556749	0.777036

Table 3: Average IoU for predicted segmentation masks.

Metrics of a subset of the DeLTA 2.0 test set is shown in table 4. The sample is an excerpt from a timeline.

	Accuracy prediction with DeLTA 2.0	Accuracy prediction with MPI	IoU prediction with DeLTA 2.0	IoU prediction with MPI
Sample000041.tif	0.725	0.661538	0.689322	0.214529
Sample000042.tif	0.707692	0.646154	0.691712	0.239165
Sample000043.tif	0.686538	0.630769	0.701916	0.230423
Sample000044.tif	0.673077	0.613462	0.716788	0.254935
Sample000045.tif	0.648077	0.598077	0.721026	0.288496
Sample000046.tif	0.621154	0.567308	0.728674	0.292785
Sample000047.tif	0.590385	0.536538	0.734365	0.304093
Sample000048.tif	0.559615	0.503846	0.735894	0.303862
Sample000049.tif	0.526923	0.45	0.741001	0.315061

Table 4: Excerpt values of metrics for DeLTA 2.0 test set prediction segmentation masks.

It can be summarized that the DeLTA 2.0 trained model performs better on the DeLTA 2.0 test set than the MPI trained model. This was expected, since the DeLTA 2.0 test set has a more diverse test set and more images of high complexity. Since the samples in table 4 belong to a timeline, the number of cells increase from *Sample000041.tif* to *Sample000049.tif*, hence for both models the pixel accuracy decreases with the growing number of cells in the timeline, while the IoU is even increasing with the growing cluster, i.e. while the correct prediction of pixels belonging to a cell or not belonging to a cell is decreasing the localization of correct predictions is increasing.

To visualize the metrics and the performance behind this a script presented in [61, 62] was adapted shown in listing 26.

```

62 """
63 @author: https://github.com/kiteco/kite-python-blog-post-code/tree/master/image-segmentation
64 getting confusion matrix values
65
66 Parameters
67 -----
68 array : groundtruth image
69 array: predicted segmentation mask
70 -----
71 Returns
72 dict : 4 boolean numpy arrays with True at TP, FP, FN, TN
73
74 """
75 def get_confusion_matrix_interp_mats(groundtruth, predicted):
76     confusion_matrix_arrs = {}
77
78     groundtruth_inverse = np.logical_not(groundtruth)
79     predicted_inverse = np.logical_not(predicted)
80
81     confusion_matrix_arrs['tp'] = np.logical_and(groundtruth, predicted)
82     confusion_matrix_arrs['tn'] = np.logical_and(groundtruth_inverse, predicted_inverse)
83     confusion_matrix_arrs['fp'] = np.logical_and(groundtruth_inverse, predicted)
84     confusion_matrix_arrs['fn'] = np.logical_and(groundtruth, predicted_inverse)
85
86     return confusion_matrix_arrs
87
88
89
90 """
91 @author: https://github.com/kiteco/kite-python-blog-post-code/tree/master/image-segmentation
92 creating overlay
93
94 Parameters
95 -----
96 array : original image
97 array : groundtruth image
98 array: predicted segmentation mask
99 float: alpha, opacity for overlay
100 dict: colors for overlay
101     'tp': (0, 255, 255), #cyan
102     'fp': (255, 0, 255), #magenta
103     'fn': (255, 255, 0), #yellow
104     'tn': (0, 0, 0) #black
105 -----
106 Returns
107 array : overlay the 'image' with a color mask where TP, FP, FN, TN are
108     each a color given by the 'colors' dictionary
109
110 """
111 def get_confusion_matrix_overlaid_mask(image, groundtruth, predicted, alpha=0.5, colors={'tp':
112     (0, 255, 255), 'fp': (255, 0, 255), 'fn': (255, 255, 0), 'tn': (0, 0, 0)}):
113     image = cv2.cvtColor(image, cv2.COLOR_GRAY2RGB)
114     masks = get_confusion_matrix_interp_mats(groundtruth, predicted)
115     color_mask = np.zeros_like(image)
116     for label, mask in masks.items():
117         color = colors[label]
118         mask_rgb = np.zeros_like(image)
119         mask_rgb[mask != 0] = color
120         color_mask += mask_rgb
121     return cv2.addWeighted(image, alpha, color_mask, 1 - alpha, 0)

```

Listing 26: Functions to create a colored overlay of TP, FP, FN and TN of the predicted segmentation map.

The functions were executed on the first and the last sample listed in table 4. The color reference for the overlay is:

- TP: cyan
- FP: magenta

- FN: yellow
- TN: black

The

(a) Overlay on *Sample000041.tif* predicted by DeLTA 2.0 trained model.

(b) Overlay on *Sample000041.tif* predicted by MPI trained model.

Figure 42: Overlay in *Sample000041.tif*.

(a) Overlay on *Sample000049.tif* predicted by DeLTA 2.0 trained model.

(b) Overlay on *Sample000049.tif* predicted by MPI trained model.

Figure 43: Overlay in *Sample000049.tif*.

Figure 42 and figure 43 show that the DeLTA 2.0 trained model makes less false predictions, especially it does not predict pixels to belong to a cell, when they are not labeled as cell in the groundtruth. The MPI trained model does make false predictions, where the FP predictions result in being trained to have smaller borders, which can be seen in the small magenta colored border on the cells. Figure 42 and figure 43 illustrate that the MPI trained model learned to label more pixels as belonging to a cell.

Metrics of a subset of the MPI test set is shown in table 5. The sample is an excerpt from the test set and the images belong to one timeline.

	Accuracy prediction with DeLTA 2.0	Accuracy prediction with MPI	IoU prediction with DeLTA 2.0	IoU prediction with MPI
2101_pos02cha00fra000001.tif	0.908691	0.908691	0.530962	0.751995
2101_pos02cha00fra000002.tif	0.899902	0.898926	0.524551	0.728045
2101_pos02cha00fra000003.tif	0.90332	0.90332	0.534501	0.76146
2101_pos02cha00fra000004.tif	0.895508	0.896484	0.597861	0.816228
2101_pos02cha00fra000005.tif	0.875977	0.875977	0.595204	0.81387
2101_pos02cha00fra000006.tif	0.85791	0.85791	0.615298	0.815367
2101_pos02cha00fra000007.tif	0.834961	0.828613	0.598283	0.78833
2101_pos02cha00fra000008.tif	0.816895	0.816895	0.586569	0.772647
2101_pos02cha00fra000009.tif	0.806152	0.806152	0.559071	0.753162
2101_pos02cha00fra000010.tif	0.789551	0.789551	0.57749	0.754027
2101_pos02cha00fra000011.tif	0.764648	0.764648	0.586021	0.769724
2101_pos02cha00fra000012.tif	0.734375	0.734863	0.616395	0.787263
2101_pos02cha00fra000013.tif	0.720703	0.720703	0.577011	0.768318
2101_pos02cha00fra000014.tif	0.71582	0.71582	0.553222	0.750661
2101_pos02cha00fra000015.tif	0.716797	0.716797	0.561886	0.753357

Table 5: Excerpt values of metrics for MPI test set prediction segmentation masks.

The pixel accuracy on the MPI test set is similar for predictions of both models. Since the images belong to a timeline the clusters in the image grow from *2101_pos02cha00fra000001.tif* to *2101_pos02cha00fra000015.tif*. Hence in both prediction sets, the pixel accuracy decreases with the number of cells in the image. The IoU of the MPI trained model outperforms the IoU of the DeLTA 2.0 trained model, in both cases the number of cells does not affect the metric. The fact that the accuracy for predicted segmentation masks of both models is similar while the IoU for the predicted segmentation masks differs can be explained by the unbalanced representation of the two classes in the images, as explained in section 2.4.1. While accuracy is affected by the imbalance, IoU is a measure of similarity between the groundtruth and the predicted segmentation map by measuring the ratio of area of overlap and area of union as defined in equation 3 and is not affected by the class imbalance. Hence the accuracy and IoU scores show that our dataset does have a class imbalance which means that IoU is the more meaningful metric.

To visualize the metrics and the performance the functions in listing 26 were applied.

(a) Overlay on *2101_pos02cha00fra000001.tif* predicted by DeLTA 2.0 trained model.

(b) Overlay on *2101_pos02cha00fra000001.tif* predicted by MPI trained model.

Figure 44: Overlay in *2101_pos02cha00fra000001.tif*.

(a) Overlay on *2101_pos02cha00fra000015.tif* predicted by DeLTA 2.0 trained model.

(b) Overlay on *2101_pos02cha00fra000015.tif* predicted by MPI trained model.

Figure 45: Overlay in *2101_pos02cha00fra000015.tif*.

Figure 44 and figure 45 show that the DeLTA 2.0 trained model makes more FP predictions because of the less accurate segmentation of the cells which can be determined by the yellow border around the cells where the DeLTA 2.0 model predicts broader borders. Comparing figure 44a with figure 45a illustrates that this behaviour is not connected to the numbers of cells in the cluster.

9.1 Performance evaluation

The model trained on the MPI dataset does not perform well on the DeLTA 2.0 dataset, but this was to be expected and improving the performance on this dataset was not the goal of the retraining. Figure 42 and figure 43 illustrates that the MPI trained model learned different features. When segmenting images of the MPI dataset with the model trained with the MPI created training data the segmentation shows improvement compared to the DeLTA 2.0 trained model with regard to our goal to get a more accurate segmentation of the cells. This is shown by the metrics in table 2, 3 and table 5 as well as in figure 44 and figure 45. In conclusion the retraining succeeded in increasing the accurate segmentation of the cells in the predicted segmentation mask of the MPI trained model compared with the predicted segmentation mask of the DeLTA 2.0 trained model without compromising the separation of the cells. This leads to the conclusion that the training data is a major factor in generating segmentation maps and the training data should focus on the features important for further attention. In our case where we wanted to have the possibility to get more accurate measurements of the cells, the retraining with a training dataset where the cells were segmented more accurately than in the original training dataset succeeded in generating segmentation masks that are not as focused on the borders. Hence the analysis of what problem needs to be solved and of the data available is a major part and equally important as the selection of the DL architecture and choice of parameters. This means that in DL projects there has to be an awareness of the importance of the analysis and data preparation part, which is time consuming and often still requires manual labour.

10 Conclusion

This project was intended to be the groundwork to create a DL pipeline for segmentation, tracking and analysis of bacteria in timelapse microscopy, where segmentation as the first step is of major importance. By generating training data and succeeding in retraining the DL model and improving the metrics for the presented problem we provided the first step for such a pipeline and laid the ground for more possible experiments.

The result of the retraining shows that training data has an impact on the performance of the model. This process is a challenging task as section 6 describes. The analysis of data formats and determining a workflow to prepare the data proved to be more complex than expected. A general challenge for DL tasks is to determine which features are important. As described the DeLTA 2.0 dataset had a different focus, which generated the need for our own dataset. For creating this dataset the intention was to use tools to try to automate this task as much as possible, but the automation of generating segmentation masks for training is not developed far enough to rely on, hence more manual labour to generate an appropriate dataset had to be done. As chapter 6 also described there are various file formats included and for direct comparison these needed to be unified which meant that the analysis of data structures and conversions had to be made. In particular creating weight maps showed the importance of close motoring and analysing the data after each step. If the training would have been done with the first generated weight maps, the model would not have learned the same weights. Creating and saving the predicted weight maps in section 6.2.3 also showed that a homogeneous dataset simplifies tasks and that scripts which are expecting such a homogeneous dataset easily break if the dataset does not fulfill this requirement. Initially I wanted to change parameters of the network to see how this affects the outcome of the training, however while preparing the data and generating the weight maps it became clear that for the retraining of the model the analysis of the images the data preparation and the monitoring of the results of each step of the workflow is essential. The missing normalization of the values in the first set of created weight maps would have resulted in the model learning different weights. For this reason I prioritized analyzing and monitoring the data over parameter adjustments of the NN.

Setting up a working environment can be a challenging task. This was simplified on the GPU cluster with the conda-forge available for Linux systems. The fact that the project had to be moved to a Windows machine while working on it could have complicated the work. Setting up this environment was done beforehand, which saved some trouble since there were compatibility issues with CUDA GPU support which could be resolved by using the DeLTA 2.0 development branch, which was proposed as a solution by the DeLTA development team. This incident shows how valuable support and exchange can be. Despite the problems in setting up the environment the scripts were transferable and could be executed without needing changes, except for the import of DeLTA 2.0 which is due to the different setup. The DeLTA 2.0 pipeline which is the core element runs stable and without the need for workarounds.

For the evaluation of image segmentation there are a lot of approaches. Section 2 already states that most evaluation is focused on the segmentation and not the performance with regard to processing time, memory or power consumption. Furthermore the metrics focus on one image at a time. Again the exchange with the DeLTA 2.0 developers gave some insights about their use of metrics and it became clear that neither is there a standardized way to

evaluate the performance, nor are there libraries or automation that evaluate segmentation in timelines of images with including the image before and after the actual timepoint. This led to the decision to stick to the most commonly used metrics for image segmentation for this project.

10.1 Lessons learned

That the analysis of the data especially the in depth analysis of the image formats and their array representations would become such a huge part of this project was not expected. The fact that it became a necessity made it clear that data analysis and preparation is a key part of a DL project and that without the clarity about the expected data and the provided data the project might fail. The results of our model trained with our generated dataset shows how much the careful creation of a dataset to train with is the base for what the model learns and that a specifically trained model might fail in more generalized tasks but perform in its specific task.

Due to the technical issues with our GPU cluster another valuable lesson was that technical equipment can fail, hence using system independent tools which can be moved easily makes working more flexible. The evaluation of tools done beforehand and the requirement to use a platform independent tool proved to be a wise decision. While ambition for a project is a great thing while working on this project it became clear that planning too many experiments would have been a mistake. More experiments would not have left us the time to monitor our data in depth through every step. Especially since the technical failure of the GPU cluster left us with 1 GPU to work with instead of 8 GPUs, which meant just one experiment at a time.

Another surprise in this project was that evaluation of segmentation is still basic and building standards for how to measure segmentation results and the performance of a network with regard to other metrics would improve the evaluation process. It also made clear that evaluating the performance of a network is highly dependent on the performed task and building guidelines for evaluation could help to create comparability.

11 Outlook

This project was intended to create groundwork to build on. The complete retraining of the model proved to be successful for our specific dataset, nevertheless there are more possibilities to explore in the future. As stated in section 6.2 the complexity of the MPI dataset could be increased to improve the performance even more. One way to create that dataset would be to cut images with multiple clusters of cells into images showing one cluster. To get a more generalized model that performs well on the MPI dataset and the DeLTA 2.0 dataset a model trained with a combined dataset could be evaluated. This also could include the omnipose dataset as suggested in section 6.2. Instead of training a model with a combined dataset, transfer learning, a technique where not all but only selected layers of the NN are retrained, would be a possibility. Furthermore the project didn't evaluate the possibilities of changing the parameters of the NN to improve its performance. This would be another interesting aspect to investigate. This might also include changes in the DeLTA 2.0 core, since some of the parameters are hard coded into DeLTA 2.0.

To build a complete pipeline there are more steps to be done than optimizing the segmentation.

The next step would be to examine the tracking model and the possibilities to analyse the images with the DeLTA 2.0 pipeline and determine if DeLTA 2.0 gathers all the data needed for the research done with the model organism and the options to evaluate and export this data. For information not implemented in DeLTA 2.0 the options of gathering them by implementing them in an additional package like the deltahelpers package in this project has to be considered. Another possibility to implement more functions would be a fork project or a collaboration with the DeLTA 2.0 development team, if the functions might be of use for other research groups as well.

The final goal would be to implement a complete image processing pipeline which is easy to use for researchers not proficient in scripting and DL by integrating the model into a GUI. For this existing tools which allow to load DL models should be evaluated and tested.

Glossary

Artificial Intelligence (AI) The effort to automate intellectual tasks normally performed by humans [30]. 1, 10

Deep Learning (DL) Deep Learning: Specialisation of Machine Learning, where the network extracts the relevant features [63].. 1, 2

features Feature: one of the values contained in a sample, a piece of information about the content of an image. Also used to refer to a particular structure in an input that a filter tries to detect [11]. 5

Graphical user interface (GUI) Graphical user interface: visual representation of a program for users to interact with the program [23]. 21

Graphics processing unit (GPU) Graphics processing unit: computer hardware which computes the graphical output and processes graphical computations [23]. 12

Machine Learning (ML) Machine Learning: artificial generation of knowledge from experience based on algorithms [63]. 10

Machine Learning (NN) Neural Network: model in DL with multiple layers of artificial neurons [30].. 4

Rectified linear unit (ReLU) Rectified linear unit: An activation function widely used in CNNs and image processing [33]. 15

A File Appendix

The file appendix contains the training datasets used in this thesis, the test splits and the predicted datasets. It also includes the deltahelpers python package and the created scripts for the retraining and evaluation. Furthermore the DeLTA 2.0 version running on the windows environment was added to ensure the experiment can be recreated. The csv files with the calculated metrics are also included in the appendix. The zip archive can be found here on zenodo [57] or on the USB drive attached to the print version.

The zip archive is structured as follows:

```
img_seg_pseudomonas_fluorescens
  \assets
    \delta
      \models:
      model files saved from training the NN with the DeLTA dataset
    \tests:
    test split and predictions of the DeLTA dataset
    \trainingssets:
    DeLTA training dataset used in the retraining, original folder structure
    of DeLTA assets
  \mpi
    \model:
    model files saved from training the NN with the MPI dataset
    \tests:
    test split and predictions of the MPI dataset
    \trainingssets:
    MPI training dataset
  \config:
  config files
  \delta-dev:
  DeLTA 2.0 implementation used in the project
  \metrics:
  calculated metrics of the predicted segmentation maps of the test sets
  \scripts:
  scripts created for analyzing data, retraining the NN, saving predicted segmen-
  tation masks and evaluate the performance
    \deltahelpers:
    Python package to save reusable functions
    \training-rename:
    locally used script to rename files from one naming convention to another
```

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